

Decentring the Study of Migrant
Returns and Return Policies

Synthesis report

WP4: Return migration governance in the African and Middle Eastern regions and the role of the EU

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D4.1 - April 2025

Co-funded by

Deliverable information

Project acronym	GAPs - De-centring the Study of Migrant Returns and Readmission Policies in Europe and Beyond
Project no.	101094341
WP	4
Deliverable title	Synthesis report
Deliverable type	R – Document, report
Version	V2
Date	3 April 2025
Responsible partners	Radboud University
Authors	Nora Stel, Marieke van Houte & Selma Blanken (Radboud University)
Dissemination level	Public

Revision history

Version	Date	Authors	Changes
v1	31 January 2025	Stel, Van Houte & Blanken	First full draft, based on country dossiers and various WP4 partner workshops and intra-WP communication
v2	3 April 2025	Stel, Van Houte & Blanken	Final version, revised after comments provided by WP4 partners and external reviewers Gerasimos Tsourapas and Nassim Majidi

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This research was conducted under the Horizon Europe project ‘GAPS: De-centring the Study of Migrant Returns and Readmission Policies in Europe and Beyond’ (101094341). The sole responsibility of this publication lies with the authors. The European Union is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein. Any enquiries regarding this publication should be sent to the author(s) at: nora.stel@ru.nl and/or marieke.vanhoute@ru.nl

Cite as:

Stel, N., Van Houte, M., & Blanken, S. (2025) Synthesis report – Return migration governance in the African and Middle Eastern regions and the role of the EU. <i>GAPs Working Paper 2025: 5</i> . DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15166876

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List of abbreviations

AVRR	Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration
CSO	Civil Society Organization
DG-ECHO	Directorate General for Civil Protection and Humanitarian Aid Operations
DG-NEAR	Directorate General for European Neighborhood and Enlargement Negotiations
DG-HOME	Directorate General for Migration and Home Affairs
ECRE	European Council on Refugees and Exiles
EEAS	European External Action Service
EU	European Union
FRONTEX	European Border and Coast Guard Agency
GNU	Libyan Government of National Unity
ICMPD	Internal Center for Migration Policy Development
IOM	International Organization for Migration
MPRR-NA	The EU's Migrant Protection, Return and Reintegration in North Africa programme
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
OHCHR	United Nations Human Rights Office
PMM	Turkish Presidency of Migration Management
RSD	Refugee Status Determination
UNHCR	United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees
VHR	IOM's Voluntary Humanitarian Return Program

GAPs Project

GAPs is a Horizon Europe project that aims to conduct a comprehensive multidisciplinary study on the drivers of return policies and the barriers and enablers of international cooperation on return migration. The overall aim of the project is to examine the disconnects and discrepancies between expectations of return policies and their actual outcomes by de-centring the dominant, one-sided understanding of “return policymaking.” To this end, GAPs:

- examines the shortcomings of the EU’s return governance;
- analyses enablers and barriers to international cooperation, and
- explores the perspectives of migrants themselves to understand their knowledge, aspirations and experiences with return policies.

GAPs combines its decentring approach with three innovative concepts:

- a focus on return migration infrastructures, which allows the project to analyse governance fissures;
- an analysis of return migration diplomacy to understand how relations between EU Member States and third countries hinder cooperation on return; and
- a trajectory approach that uses a socio-spatial and temporal lens to understand migrant agency.

GAPs is an interdisciplinary 3-year project (2023-2026), co-coordinated by Uppsala University and the Bonn International Centre for Conflict Studies with 17 partners in 12 countries on 4 continents. GAPs' fieldwork has been conducted in 14 countries: Jordan, Lebanon, Sweden, Nigeria, Germany, Morocco, the Netherlands, Afghanistan, Poland, Georgia, Turkey, Tunisia, Greece and Iraq.

This synthesis report has been compiled in the context of the GAPs Work Package on ‘Return Migration Governance in the African and Middle Eastern Regions and the Role of the EU.’

Acknowledgements

We would like to sincerely thank all the people that have enabled and contributed to our analysis (even if our analysis and any shortcomings it may have of course remain our own). This first and foremost regards the country teams of our GAPs Work Package on ‘Return Migration Governance in the African and Middle Eastern Regions and the Role of the EU,’ whose country dossiers and co-analyses form the basis of this synthesis report. GAPs WP4 colleagues were an amazing soundboard and inspiration. We are also grateful to Nassim Majidi and Gerasimos Tsourapas for providing valuable input. GAPs coordinators Zeynep Şahin-Mencütek and Soner Barthoma have been incredibly supportive in thinking along.

Funding acknowledgement

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. In addition, GAPs benefit from funding provided by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government’s Horizon Europe funding guarantee. The Canadian research component of this project is undertaken, in part, thanks to funding from the Canada Excellence Research Chairs Program of the Government of Canada.

1. Executive Summary

This report explores **return migration governance in the African and Middle Eastern regions and the role of the EU** by looking at the governance of coerced returns from Turkey, Lebanon, Jordan, and Iraq to Syria; from Morocco, Tunisia, and Libya to Nigeria; and from Iran and Turkey to Afghanistan.

- This study is situated in a **CONTEXT** where the migration management of the African and Middle Eastern host countries under study has increasingly focused on return.
 - This is a consequence of the gradually more protracted nature of specific displacement situations.
 - It also follows from the longer term development of the shift in EU migration management towards externalization and containment. This shift has undermined the circularity of mobility between and within regions. Regional host countries increasingly faced an ‘integration or return’ logic.
- The **CHARACTERISTICS** of the ensuing return migration governance in the African and Middle Eastern Regions differ across contexts.
 - In general, the report observes that the **type** of return pursued by these countries on the most significant **scale** is self-return, whereby humanitarian migrants are pushed to individually and independently return to their country of origin.
 - This happens through mutually reinforcing push factors created by **policies and practices, or the absence thereof**, that produce legal and socio-economic exclusion and (structural) violence, resulting in both irregularization and subsequent marginalization.
 - This combined **irregularization and marginalization** does not merely generate self-return. It also coerces migrants to participate in facilitated return. By criminalizing (particular groups of) migrants, such policies and practices also serve as a legitimation for deportation – a dynamic further exacerbated by the securitization of migration management.
 - Overall, coerced return migration governance in the countries under study is **highly informal and opaque**, with the more overly coerced types of return (pushbacks and deportations) particularly lacking systematic monitoring and transparent reporting. This partly follows from the complex assemblage of **actors** involved, ranging from state authorities to hybrid political parties, and international organizations.
- The **DRIVERS** of coerced return migration governance in the countries under study partially follow from domestic **interests**, where real and politically instrumentalized socio-economic pressures and securitized rhetoric generate public demand for return.
 - They are also rooted in international interests, where EU donor diplomacy focused on containment and preventing onward movement on the one hand contributes to a regional context favouring return and on the other hand imposes a focus on particular types of returns (self-return and facilitated return).
 - The EU also crucially shapes the **capacities** of regional host states for coerced return migration governance – which vary widely per context. Such capacity-building is officially designated for self-return and facilitated return but is often also leveraged for pushbacks and deportation. This comes in the form of policy advice, training, and material support, often channelled through international organizations.

- The **CONSEQUENCES** of coerced return migration governance in the countries under study include:
 - the strategic blurring of different forms of more or less overtly coerced return, that are presented as voluntary; a systematic undermining of humanitarian migrants' and refugees' **protection**, including erosion of the non-refoulement principle;
 - the sabotaging of **mobility** through the prevention of onward movement as well as re-entry after coerced return;
 - and making human mobility a key agenda item for **diplomacy** in the region, in which enforcing, resisting, and instrumentalizing return plays an ever more central role.

Keywords: Africa, Middle East, EU, coerced return migration, governance

2. Introduction

Since the vast majority of migrants and refugees move and reside in and among countries in the immediate region of their origin countries (Bank and Fröhlich 2018; Chimni 1998; İçduygu and Nimer 2020; Ihlamur-Öner 2022), return migration will also predominantly take place within the region of countries in crisis (ACP 2013; Tsourapas 2017; Van Houte and Davids 2014). Yet, scholarly concerns have overwhelmingly focused on the minority of migrants who travelled further afield, in particular to the European Union (EU), and return from there to their regions of origin (Cleton and Schweitzer 2021; Kalir and Wissink 2016). Relatively little attention has been given to the return policies of neighbouring hosting states within the African and (wider) Middle Eastern region.

Disregarding this regional dimension puts a Eurocentric bias on the study of return migration governance. Regional return governance, moreover, both shapes and is shaped by the externalization and return migration policies of the EU (Adamson and Tsourapas 2018; Freier, Micinski, and Tsourapas 2021; Larik and Sahoo 2018). On the one hand, the EU's deterrence and externalization 'partnerships' fundamentally affect return diplomacies, infrastructures, and trajectories in its neighbouring regions (Adamson and Greenhill 2023; Fakhoury and Şahin-Mencütek 2023; Olakpe 2020). On the other hand, the governance of regional returns has repercussions for the migration dynamics that the EU seeks to control, for its engagement with 'third countries,' and for the international norms on protection and non-refoulement that it claims to uphold.

To address this knowledge gap, therefore, this Work Package aims to better understand the intersections between (i) return migration governance in the African and Middle Eastern regions and (ii) the role of the European Union and its external migration policy. To this end, it poses three core research questions: (i) What characterizes return migration governance in African and Middle Eastern regions? Specifically: how are these modalities shaped by the EU's external migration policy?; (ii) What are the driving forces behind these types of return migration governance? Specifically: how are these drivers affected by the EU's external migration policy?; and (iii) What are the effects of these drivers and modalities of return migration governance in these regions, for both people and policy? Specifically: what are the implications of specific return migration governance in these regions for the EU's external migration policy?

The Work Package answers these questions for eight 'host countries' (Iraq, Jordan, Lebanon, Turkey, Iran, Morocco, Tunisia, Libya) focused on three 'origin countries' (Syria, Afghanistan, Nigeria) and producing eight country dossiers. Empirical research for these country dossiers was conducted between mid-2023 and mid-2024, meaning that our analysis does not extend beyond this period. This is particularly relevant to the analysis of return to Syria: this report regards return migration governance in the period preceding the fall of the Assad regime. In general, the analyses synthesized in this report broadly cover the last two decades – where return to Syria concerns a demarcated period (2011-2024) and return to Nigeria and Afghanistan extends further back in time. Throughout the report, we dedicate attention to specific turning points in these different return governance cases.

In line with the governance approach introduced below, we understand the 'EU' as a comprehensive assemblage of various institutions and actors (Cooper and Nimer 2023; Fakhoury and Şahin-Mencütek 2023; Olakpe 2020). When it comes to EU external migration policy, this includes its diplomatic services (EEAS) and its delegations and the European

Commission and its various directorates (DG-HOME, DG-NEAR, DG-ECHO) and agencies (FRONTEX) in Brussels as well as in partner countries. In our comprehensive reading of EU migration governance, we also consider the mutual impact of EU and member-state policy, practice, and rhetoric. In addition, we understand the various partners which the EU funds and with which it coordinates in implementing its external migration policy – most notably the IOM (International Organization for Migration) and ICMPD (the International Center for Migration Policy Development) – as part of the broader EU assemblage we refer to when exploring the impact of the EU on return migration governance in the African and Middle Eastern regions. The EU as such, moreover, operates as part of a broader ‘international community’ in which other states, like the United States and the United Kingdom, also shape the context of its external migration policy. Within this assemblage, there are contradictions and tensions and the EU thus cannot be considered a unitary actor. When referring to EU policy in this report, then, we refer to the overall logics and overarching direction of its comprehensive policy, practice, and rhetoric.

Our analytical framework centres around the notion of return migration governance (Olakpe 2020, 3). Governance here refers to the ‘complex of formal and informal institutions, mechanisms, relationships, and processes’ (Colebatch 2009, 60) through which actors exercise power and ‘shape the field of action of others’ (Cooper and Nimer 2024, 785). As reflected in our research questions and informed by the specific literature on return, we have operationalized this governance perspective by examining the characteristics of such return migration governance - particularly its scale, modality, actors, policies, and practices; the drivers of return governance – specifically the interests and capacities that shape it; and the consequences of return migration governance – focussing on protection, mobility, and diplomacy. Note that in this Work Package the focus is on governance actors. The experiences and agency of humanitarian migrants themselves is central to Work Packages 7 and 8 of the GAPs project.

The outline of this report roughly follows this analytical approach. We start with reflections on methods, then proceed with a section on the context where we discuss our position on the concept of ‘migrant’ and provide an overview of the reasons for migration and the governance of initial arrival and settlement for the case-studies central to this Work Package and report. We then move to our findings, consisting of sections on (1) the characteristics and (2) drivers of return migration governance in the African and Middle Eastern regions, including the role of the EU in return migration governance in those regions, followed by (3) the consequences of return migration governance in the African and Middle Eastern regions and the role of the EU for protection, im/mobilities and geopolitics and diplomacy. The report then concludes with some reflections that position our findings in the literature.

3. Methods

Research in this Work Package is carried out using an embedded-multiple case study design, in which cases are selected for diversity (encompassing variation in return types) and representativeness (including main host countries in return systems that are salient to Europe, i.e., Africa and the broader Middle East). Dedicated country teams have studied return migration from Jordan, Lebanon, Turkey, and Iraq to Syria; from Morocco, Tunisia, and Libya to Nigeria; and from Turkey and Iran to Afghanistan. Return migration governance has been

analyzed on the level of the returning country, with explicit attention to actors in the origin country and the EU that might affect these dynamics, in the eight country dossiers (the Turkey dossier analyzes returns of Syrian as well as Afghan people) that are attached to this synthesis report for reference. These country dossiers follow the same outline and the research they are based on is based on the same design in terms of data generation and data analysis.

Data for the research in each country dossier are generated through document analysis (a minimum of 20 documents – including academic papers, expert reports, and media coverage – have been analyzed in-depth per country dossier) and semi-structured, in-depth expert interviews with state authorities, international organizations, and civil society actors (at least 10 such interviews have been conducted for each country dossier). Data was coded iteratively. Coding had a primarily deductive starting point, where a common codebook based on a shared conceptual framework developed to answer the three core questions on the characteristics, drivers, and consequences of particular modalities of governing return that were listed above was used to categorize and organize empirical findings for each country case. Additionally, data was coded inductively for each country case, highlighting emerging themes that were not included in the codebook but that nevertheless surfaced as contextually relevant. Research on the country level as reflected in the country dossiers has been subject to ethical review of the host institutions of the individual researchers conducting the country-specific research. The core concern here has been to ensure (oral) informed consent for interviews on the basis of full anonymity of interlocutors.

During both the design and implementation phases of the country-level research, the Work Package has adopted an integrated, decentered approach. The scope and focus (and core research questions) of the Work Package have been developed collaboratively by the GAPs project coordinators and the Work Package coordinators. These research questions have subsequently been finetuned and operationalized in close coordination with all country partners during two online Work Package workshops. The first workshop focused on streamlining and discussing document research. The second workshop focused on implementing and contextualizing interview research.

This synthesis report is based on the eight country dossiers compiled in this way. Unless indicated otherwise through references, all information and analysis provided with regard to a specific country is based on the corresponding country dossier. In this report, we aim to compare and synthesize the insights presented in the different country dossiers to identify common patterns as well as diverging dynamics for each of the three core research questions of this Work Package. The authors of this synthesis report have extensively reviewed the country dossiers at multiple stages of the analysis and writing process and discussed them in-depth with the respective country teams to ensure thorough and contextualized understanding. They furthermore compiled and juxtaposed all relevant country specific information for each dimension of the shared Work Package codebook, thereby creating a combined comparative dataset to guide synthesis analysis for this report. Subsequently, two additional Work Package workshops were organized to present emerging analyses for this synthesis report to the respective country teams to solicit feedback and soundboard core findings.

4. Context: Outmigration, arrival and reception and the emerging need for return migration governance

In understanding the context of return migration governance in the countries under study, the (perceived) drivers of initial outmigration are crucial as these inform the initiatives developed to govern return. This section therefore first engages with the usual distinction in such drivers of initial outmigration between economic and political considerations and the related categorization of migrants and refugees. Second, it offers a succinct overview of the core drivers of outmigration for the three origin countries central to this report.

Core observations

- We see **shifts** from **solidarity** inspired by cultural affiliation and existing socio-economic ties towards more **reluctant** hosting and more pressure on return in situations of protracted displacement;
- We also see a **differentiated solidarity** (where the same host country may develop different return governance towards different (national or socio-economic) migrant populations);
- Alongside the **protractedness of displacement**, governance include the institutionalization of **temporariness and precarity of protection** signalled by temporary protection or 'guest status' rather than formal asylum or integration;
- The **positioning of origin countries** to which irregularized humanitarian migrants are supposed to return depends on the relations with particular host/returning states, and the envisioned political and socio-economic impact of return.

Humanitarian migration

The legal distinction between 'refugees' and other 'migrants' is often empirically untenable for various reasons. First, literature shows that the legal category of 'refugee' is too narrow and leaves 'protection gaps' (Türk and Dowd 2014) for people escaping conflict and violence. In our case this means that even though Syria, Afghanistan, and Nigeria all rank 'low' to 'very low' (Nigeria 144, Syria 161 and Afghanistan 163 out of 163) on the Global Peace Index (Institute for Economics and Peace 2023), and populations from all three countries are considered refugees under the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees' (UNHCR) mandate, Syrians and Afghans are more easily considered by international law/human rights organizations as refugees while Nigerians are not – something that is often related to geopolitical considerations towards the country of origin (Almasri 2023).

Second, notwithstanding international law, host countries also categorize these groups differently, leading to different levels of hospitality. Despite the violence and conflict-related hardships in Nigeria, Nigerians are often perceived and treated as labour migrants and transit migrants rather than refugees in the North African countries under study. Turkey hosts both populations displaced from Afghanistan and Syria, two of the largest refugee populations worldwide, with around 6,4 million refugees each in 2023 (UNHCR 2023a). However, Syrian refugees are considered as refugees, while Afghan triggers for displacement tend to be delegitimized, leading to less registration of Afghan refugees, and more apprehensions and deportations (Almasri 2023). According to Almasri (2023) this difference in host attitude is related to donor attention and the EU-Turkey 'statement' that rewarded and re-enforced

“artificial distinctions between Syrian refugees and refugees from other conflict zones, including Iraq and Afghanistan” (Almasri 2023).

In this report, encompassing the notion of ‘irregularized migrants’ (Şahin-Mencütek 2024a), we use the term humanitarian migrants to recognize that all those displaced from Nigeria, Syria, and Afghanistan were so in the context of violence and threats to their livelihood, despite differentiated recognition in international law and their host countries (Talleraas, Brekke, and Buhr 2022; van Houte, Kaşlı, and Leerkes 2023) when these people face expulsion. At the same time, we recognize in this report that legal categories such as ‘refugee’ that are assigned to people shape empirical reality as they partly determine variations in reception, hosting and return migration governance by reception countries. People considered refugees usually benefit from more legal protection from forced return than other humanitarian migrants. Both domestic and international political considerations may grant people who are considered refugees more de facto protection from physical expulsion.

When people are considered refugees, the question of whether return risks being refoulement - the act of expelling or returning a refugee back to the territory where they face violence or persecution (OHCHR 2018) – becomes relevant. While, as we observe in this report, safety considerations may not significantly shape the interest of host country authorities to return people, it does shape the types of return governance that are used and the ways in which return is presented or framed, as host states are under pressure to at least appear to nominally respect the principle of non-refoulement – and are hence limited to return that can be claimed to be voluntary (Ahouga 2024). Conversely, when returning people are not considered as refugees, host country authorities seem less concerned about voluntariness and are more explicitly using deportation narratives.

Last, the complexity of ‘mixed’ migration ‘flows’ also transpires in return governance. For instance, where conflict-induced displacement follows existing labour-related migration patterns, as for example in the case of Syrian people in Lebanon and Afghans in Turkey and Iran, political as well as popular conceptions of ‘refugeeness’ have tended to be more contested: host communities sometimes had a harder time considering these migrants, with which they were familiar, suddenly as ‘refugees.’ This has impacted refugee protection and in some cases incentivized premature return.

Our choice to focus our study on the governance of return migration on the coercive dimensions of such governance is in line with the overall GAPs focus (Şahin-Mencütek et al. 2023, 8-9) and follows from our normative alignment with international humanitarian, refugee, and human rights law (Tan and Gammeltoft-Hansen 2020; Şahin-Mencütek and Triandafyllidou 2025). This allows us to foreground that while different types of return may be legally allowed under particular conditions and/or have significant popular and political support in host countries, they can nevertheless be problematic in light of the broad humanitarian obligations stipulated by international law.

Arrival and reception in host countries, return governance by origin countries

In the below sections, we provide a brief overview of the main reasons why people have decided to leave their country of origin in the first place; how they have been received in the country they moved to; how their potential return is governed by the interests and capacities of their country of origin; and how these considerations have changed over time. These snapshots are

based on the relevant context information provided in the respective country dossiers and the additional references cited and aim to highlight the regional context shaping return migration governance that is often overlooked in Euro-centric accounts on inter-regional return migration governance.

Leaving Nigeria, arriving in Morocco, Libya, and Tunisia

Leaving Nigeria

Although the EU considers Nigeria a ‘safe country,’ many Nigerians continue to leave. Outmigration from Nigeria is driven by a combination of socio-economic, political, and environmental factors. The country faces economic instability, with high unemployment rates – particularly among younger generations – persistent poverty, and growing inequalities (Arhin-Sam 2019). Social aspirations, such as better education and improved living standards, also significantly influence migration decisions. Moreover, political unrest, especially in the north due to insurgent activities by groups like Boko Haram since the early 2000s, drives individuals to flee violence and insecurity. Environmental challenges, including droughts and floods, disrupt agricultural livelihoods, pushing rural Nigerians to seek opportunities abroad, often heading North towards countries like Libya, Tunisia, and Morocco (on the broader regional context see: Adesina 2021).

Arrival and reception governance in Morocco, Libya, and Tunisia

Amongst host countries for Nigerian migrants, Libya, Tunisia and Morocco, there are notable differences in patterns of reception and arrival. Interestingly, we see that in the past decades, Libya and Morocco have undergone opposite shifts in their roles and approaches towards migration. Libya, once a key immigration hub due to its oil wealth that attracted labour from across Africa, has become a transit country for sub-Saharan Africans heading to Europe since the fall of Gaddafi in 2011 – a watershed moment for return migration governance. In contrast, Morocco, historically seen as an easy transit point to Europe, has shifted gradually into a destination country after significant policy reforms, including blocking transit migration to Spain, and centralized and large-scale integration and regularisation of migrants, after which transit migration to Europe was significantly redirected through Tunisia and Libya.

Despite the different immigration policies, in Libya and Tunisia, Sub-Sahara African migrants find themselves in marginalized positions, where they face systemic racism, compounded by xenophobic violence and impunity as well as limited access to employment, unsanitary living conditions, including water and sanitation issues, overcrowded housing, and a lack of public services like health care. Specifically in Libya, the political vacuum that resulted from the civil war, allowed militias to gain control over crucial migration routes and detention facilities notorious for abuse and poor conditions, and exploit them for profits. In Tunisia, a wave of violence against Black Africans emerged after a racist speech by the president in 2023.

Return governance by Nigeria

Between 2019 and 2023, over 29,000 Nigerians were returned to Nigeria from a range of countries along the Central Mediterranean route, either through self-return, deportation or assisted return. Once migrants return to Nigeria, the most relevant actors engaged with the governance of their return are Nigerian government agencies – such as The Nigeria Immigration Services and The National Commission for Migrants and Internally Displaced Persons – international organisations like IOM, Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) and civil society organizations (CSOs). These organisations collaborate through initiatives

such as the EU-funded Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration (AVRR) programme that provides different kinds of logistical support, flights and reintegration support including housing, healthcare, education and livelihood assistance programs.

Despite these supporting infrastructures, significant reintegration challenges persist. Inadequate funding, limited capacity, and coordination issues among government agencies and CSOs undermine the effectiveness of support programmes. Returnees find the promised reintegration support insufficient or misaligned with their expectations, leading to disillusionment and conflict. Unrealistic hopes fostered in host countries heighten returnees' unpreparedness for Nigeria's harsh socio-economic conditions once returned. Additionally, reintegration is undermined by the lack of coherence in return strategies of North African host countries whilst reintegration policies within Nigeria are overly centralized, neglecting the diversity of sociocultural and economic conditions within Nigeria.

Leaving Syria, arriving in Turkey, Lebanon, Jordan, and Iraq

Leaving Syria

People fled Syria for variegated security reasons after the Syrian revolution turned into a globalized civil war in 2011, ranging from personal persecution to unpredictable targeting by various actors associated with the Syrian regime and generalized insecurity and indiscriminate violence related to the war. Different peaks in the war were followed by new increases in people fleeing Syria, specifically in 2015. With the conflict becoming more protracted and generalized violence eventually becoming slightly less intense, Syrian people have also left their country for reasons related to livelihoods. Overall, Syrians have tended to flee to the closest neighbouring country, but mobility has also followed established (seasonal) labour migration patterns, with many Syrians partially working in Lebanon, Turkey or Jordan or having established socio-economic networks there.

Arrival and reception governance in Lebanon, Turkey, Jordan, and Iraq

For Syrian refugees, we see differing reception patterns. In all host countries, reception is characterized by an initial open-door policy and relatively welcoming policy and practice. In Turkey and Lebanon, this initial phase was followed by more restrictive entry policies and, respectively, stringent regularization and explicit marginalization since approximately 2019. In Iraq, where Syrians are largely hosted in the Kurdistan Region of Iraq (KRI) where authorities have welcomed Syrian Kurds, partly to increase their population, legal entry was also increasingly restricted, mostly under pressure from the federal Iraqi government, and refugees unable to pay visa renewal fees were made deportable. In Jordan, decreasing international support has made refugee hosting more strained, but official entry and stay regulations have remained supportive. These dynamics, for better or worse, also appear to be informed by the relative number of refugees in the country – refugees make up approximately 23%, 11%, 4%, and 0.5% in Lebanon, Jordan, Turkey, and Iraq respectively – and the degree to which the ethnic or sectarian make-up of these refugee communities aligns with politicization along these lines in the host country – something that is of utmost relevance in Lebanon's sectarian oligopoly, non-Arab Turkey, and Iraq's Kurdistan Region, and appears less salient in Jordan.

(Non-)encampment policies appear to be an important albeit ambivalent element of the governance of arrival and reception in relation to return governance for Syrian refugees as well. Jordan hosts roughly a fifth of all Syrians in the country in UNHCR camps; Turkey

initially, in 2014, sheltered almost a third of the Syrian refugees it received in government-run camps, but started to close down such camps as of 2018, with currently less than 5% of refugees living there (Relief Web 2014). In Iraq, approximately a third of the Syrian population lived in camps. Lebanon instead opted for an explicit ‘no-camp-policy’ and refugees there were largely self-settled, some of them in ‘informal tented settlements.’

Return governance by Syria

In Syria under Assad, refugee return was considered a highly pertinent political issue by all relevant authorities. Within the Syrian regime, the most relevant actors engaging with return migration governance in the sense of policy and diplomacy were the President and his representatives and the Ministry of Foreign Affairs. These were complemented by a wide array of security agencies – such as the infamous Fourth Division of the Syrian army – involved in ad hoc and irregular return migration governance on the ground.

The main policies governing return migration from the Syrian side were article 38 of the 2013 Syrian Constitution that ensures the formal right to return. Various amnesty laws were also often referred to when Syrian goodwill towards return is assessed. This support for return was also regularly proclaimed by regime representatives in public statements and on diplomatic occasions – where they accused host countries and the international community of obstructing return (Al Jazeera 2020; Enab Baladi 2024; Middle East Monitor 2023). Some practices from the Syrian side also indicated an interest in facilitating return. This for instance regarded the ‘reconciliation process’ supposedly provided by the regime, through which potential returnees could seek various forms of safety guarantees with different Syrian authorities.

‘Guarantees’ obtained through this process often did not ensure actual protection upon return and thereby add to the very uncertainty and unsafety that prevented return. In 2022, a Syrian initiative to force Syrian people to periodically prove land and real estate ownership was also seen as intending to encourage or enforce refugees to return but had no such effect. In combination with the consistent fear to return expressed by Syrian refugees in various surveys – who recalled earlier regime statements that anyone fleeing the country would be considered a ‘traitor –’, other practices, such as the continued targeting and persecution of returnees and the maintenance of forced conscription as well as the practical vacuity of the mentioned amnesty laws, further substantiate the conclusion that while formal policy and diplomacy aimed to convey support for return, practice on the ground evidently obstructed return.

This paradox can be explained with a closer look at Syrian interests and capacities under Assad. The Syrian state was extremely weak and did not have the capacity to either manage or materially enable large-scale return and reintegration processes. Fragmentation between Syrian civil and security state institutions as well as among the wide array of Syrian security services impedes coordination with Syrian authorities on safety guarantees for returnees. They Assad’s regime’s main capacity regarded its role as a potential spoiler to return: without Syrian support for return, large-scale and durable return is impossible. It was in leveraging this role that we see the core capacity for return governance of the Syrian state and its interests revealed. With backing from their geopolitical allies, notably Russia and Iran, Syrian authorities leveraged support for return as a bargaining chip for receiving diplomatic recognition (and the related normalization of relations with and lifting of sanctions by Western states) and for receiving substantial aid for reconstruction.

Leaving Afghanistan, arriving in Iran and Turkey

Leaving Afghanistan

Due to several political waves of internal conflict and violence, along with recurring natural disasters, the Afghan refugee population is one of the highest numbers worldwide. In 1979, the Soviet Union invaded the country by a communist coup d'état. This violent shift of power was followed by decades of civil war, devastating the country, and forcing over 6 million Afghans to flee their homeland, primarily to Pakistan and Iran (Barlas 2022). In 1989, the Soviet-backed government was driven out and left Afghanistan in chaos and civil war with various parties competing for control. By 1994, the Taliban seized power, imposing strict Islamic law. The Taliban's repressive regime and ongoing violence led to a new wave of internal displacement and a significant rise in outward migration. Following the 9/11 attacks in 2001, a U.S.-led coalition invaded Afghanistan, driving out the Taliban. In the subsequent two-decade-long U.S. presence, instability persisted and many Afghans sought refuge abroad due to insecurity, poverty, and limited opportunities. In 2021, the U.S. withdrew its forces, leading to the Taliban's return to power. This resurgence was a new impulse for migration as Afghans fled Taliban revenge and feared the loss of rights, particularly for women. Humanitarian crises, economic collapse, and repression under the Taliban have continued to push people out of the country.

Arrival and reception governance in Iran and Turkey

Over the past decades, Iran has been one of the main destinations for millions of displaced Afghans and currently shelters 3.8 million Afghans, thereby hosting the largest refugee population worldwide. While 90 percent of Afghan refugees reside in Iran and Pakistan, it is a popular transit hub for a minority of Afghans to reach Turkey and Europe (Naseh 2025). The development of Iran's migration policies, and therefore the reception of Afghan migrants, reflects the continuously changing socio-political dynamics, economic realities, and diplomatic relations between Iran and Afghanistan and the broader international community. Initially, after the Soviet invasion of Afghanistan, Iran maintained an open-door policy towards Afghan migrants. This humanitarian policy response unconditionally provided Afghans with identity cards and was partly motivated by Islamic solidarity and partly due to a lack of institutional capacity to manage the arrival of migrants.

However, the large-scale influx of Afghans placed significant pressure on Iran's socioeconomic infrastructures, resulting in job market pressure, increased public expenditures, and cultural tensions. Therefore, since 1990, the Iranian government started implementing non-integration and restrictive policies to push Afghans to return. These policies involved stopping the registration of newly arrived migrants and systematically reducing the availability of public services for already registered Afghan inhabitants. The introduction of the (yearly renewable) Amayesh (logistic or preparation) registration system, facilitated a practice of attributing and denying essential services and rights, such as access to education and healthcare. Also, Iran maintains a no-go area policy that forbids certain provinces from hosting (Afghan) foreigners. This systemic precarity and exclusion from society worsened the socio-economic position of Afghans in Iran, fostering a hostile reception environment and ultimately compelling many to return to Afghanistan.

In contrast to Iran, Turkey has maintained a non-arrival policy for Afghans since 1979 – a restrictive approach that changed shape over the years but remained in place. Most Afghan migrants (94%) enter Turkey illegally via the Iranian border, citing security (48%), economic

(36%), political (12%), and religious (3%) reasons (Pouya 2022). Unlike Syrian migrants in Turkey, who are granted a Temporary Protection (TP) status, Afghans are eligible for International Protection (IP) based on the Law of Foreigners and International Protection (LFIP, 2013, #6458). However, although a limited number of Afghan migrants are granted legal documentation based on humanitarian considerations, they are often classified as irregular migrants, making their situation significantly more precarious. Afghans face forced deportations and pushbacks, with little to no access to legal aid or the ability to submit asylum claims. The intricate nature of protection mechanisms exposes them to rapid apprehension and deportation processes, further exacerbating their vulnerability. By systematically denying Afghans opportunities for legal residence, protection, and essential services, Turkey actively produces irregularity and marginalization among Afghan migrants. This exclusion is further reinforced by pervasive hostility, discrimination, xenophobia, and social exclusion. As a result of legal precarity and a rise in anti-migrant sentiments, economic and social integration challenges are an inherent part of the reception of Afghans in Turkey.

Return governance by Afghanistan

Return to Afghanistan takes place amid much larger outmigration flows. The Directorate General of Return and Reintegration, under Afghanistan's Ministry of Refugee and Reintegration, oversees issues related to the return and reintegration of displaced persons. Return of Afghan nationals is of great symbolic value to the state and is portrayed as a result of the state's successes of bringing prosperity to the country. Moreover, the state uses its collaboration with return as diplomatic leverage. The existing policy and mechanisms for reintegration include provisions such as cash assistance and land distribution. However, these mechanisms face several challenges, including the criteria used to determine the eligibility of returnees and the issues related to access to socio-economic opportunities in the areas designated for returnee settlement. Since the 2021 takeover by the Taliban, our researchers note remarkable continuity in terms of return operations, bilateral commitments, return as diplomatic leverage, and the symbolic value of return.

5. Findings

Characteristics of return migration governance in the African and Middle Eastern regions

In this section, we discuss the patterns and variations we observe for the forms and scale of return migration governance we see in the countries under study; the relevant actors involved in such governance; and the policies and practices that are developed by these actors to encourage or control various types of return.

Core observations

- The **scale** of return varies widely, but the **main type of return** is in most cases self-return as a result of irregularization, marginalization, intimidation, detention, and violence. Deportation and assisted returns are carried out on a smaller scale. Pushbacks arguably take place in many cases, but are often invisible and hard to measure or monitor;
- There is a great deal of **interaction** between these return types, which are overlapping and, in many ways, represent a **continuum or spectrum of coercion** rather than distinct practices: because of a fear of deportation, people may self-return or sign up for

assisted return. Returns that are presented as voluntary are therefore often coerced and sometimes physically forced;

- In high-capacity states, **state return governance** is highly securitized in that it is relegated to security, defence, or intelligence agencies and governed from the idea that migrants constitute a security threat – often both in a formal central way (considering the mandates for arranging and overseeing return) and in a practical local way (where state return governance aligns with popular resentment);
- **Different domains of return governance are dispersed** across different actors. In places where the state is not in control of migration governance, **non-state actors** step in, creating an opaque field of return;
- **Normative protection** aspects are upheld by UNHCR and NGOs but often not integrated in **capacity-related implementation** by actors such as the IOM and ICMPD and state actors;
- Where formal return **policies** exist on a **national level**, their **local interpretation or implementation** can vary widely. Rather than being directly implemented, such policies can operate as a blanket legitimization for all kinds of local practices of eviction, expulsion, and exploitation;
- While some return types – predominantly self-return and assisted return – are **grounded in law** and policy, the legal or official political mandates for other return types, particularly deportation and pushbacks, are far more **elusive** and these are guided more by practice;
- When it comes to Syrian humanitarian migrants especially, we observe a **disconnect** between extensive public discourses about the **voluntariness** of return and a routine covert practice of coerced return. Institutionally, while the official focus is on assisted return, the same programmes often build capacity and infrastructures for deportations.
- The degree of **political consensus** on return governance shapes the form that return governance takes. In Lebanon and Turkey, various political parties and alliances are engaged in a race to the bottom in terms of pushing for returns, while in Jordan there is a centralized imposed consensus to refrain from enforcing returns.

Types and scale of Return

In this section, we explore the different type, size and significance of coerced returns and how they have developed over time and across the different host country contexts central to this report. Here, we follow the understanding of return coercion as a continuum or spectrum, as developed in the overarching GAPs framework (Şahin-Mencütek et al. 2023, 13).

Types

Based on the cases studies and previous research we identify four main types of coerced return in the context of return migration governance. These types follow from the ‘typology of involuntary returns’ developed by Şahin-Mencütek and Triandafyllidou (2025) along the spectrum of ‘pushing, imposing, and incentivizing’ return policies and practices. Şahin-Mencütek and Triandafyllidou (2025) define coercion as the absence of ‘freedom of choice’ to make ‘informed decisions,’ which includes comprehensive forms of structural violence and the presence of significant socio-economic push factors in the form of irregularization and exclusion.

In many of the countries studied, governance authorities as well as significant parts of the public support various policies and practices of pushing humanitarian migrants to return to

their country of origin – or more broadly just away from their current host country – even in instances where this breach the non-refoulement principle. In line with the literature that states that mobility decisions without legal and/or viable options to stay cannot be voluntary (Şahin-Mencütek and Triandafyllidou 2025), we have in our typology opted to steer away from the often-used terminology of ‘voluntariness’ and instead highlight the diverse forms of coercion underlying return (Şahin-Mencütek et al. 2023, 8; Ahouga 2024, 2).

1. **Self-return** – self-organized return as a result of social/economic/political exclusion and irregularization, marginalization, repression and/or (the state’s blind eye to) violence to prompt self-organized return or onward migration – resonates with what Sahin-Mencütek & Triandafyllidou (2025) call ‘incentivizing’ returns. This concerns returns that people have arranged and conducted individually without support from state agencies. Despite there not being physical or direct coercion of mobility, these self-returns are a result of an strategy to make life difficult for irregularized migrants in the host country and therefore push people out;

Box 1: Self-return from Turkey to Syria

Turkey in many instances pressures Syrians into “self-return,” maintaining the appearance of voluntary returns while leveraging indirect coercion through irregularization. Although the government claimed to respect the non-refoulement in the pre-Assad fall era, there was a significant intimidation policy towards refugees which made them precarious and transformed their legal stay into an irregularized presence. Syrians under Temporary Protection face significant challenges, including economic hardship due to restricted access to formal employment, low wages, and poor working conditions, which push many to consider returning to Syria. Social pressures, such as rising anti-migrant sentiment, discrimination, and incidents of hostility, further isolated Syrians and discouraged integration. The legal framework compounded this precarity, with the temporary nature of TP creating uncertainty and limiting long-term stability. Policies such as restrictions on movement, address verification exercises, and limitations on new registrations in certain areas leave many Syrians without access to essential services or legal protection. Additionally, securing or maintaining Temporary Protection registration has become increasingly difficult, further undermining refugees’ ability to remain in Turkey. Thus, although returns are labelled as voluntary, they are often shaped by coercive factors, such as deteriorating living conditions, lack of integration prospects, and promises of improved circumstances in “safe zones” in northern Syria.

(Source: Turkey Country Dossier)

2. **Assisted return** – which includes all forms of return organized and implemented by state actors and/or their international partners (most often IOM and UNHCR) in so-called Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration (AVRR) programmes – is, according to Şahin-Mencütek & Triandafyllidou (2025), also a form of ‘incentivizing’ returns. These programmes are nominally ‘voluntary’ in the sense that people formally consent to their return and they are not physically forced (while still subject to the same ‘incentivization’ as self-return). Following common practice in the academic literature, we use the term assisted return to refer to these AVRR programmes to not reproduce the in many cases misleading notion of voluntariness.

Box 2: Assisted return from Tunisia to Nigeria

Assisted return from Tunisia mainly takes place for migrants who were intercepted at sea on their way to Europe. Sent back to Tunisia, they face an unwelcoming policy by the Tunisian government, captured by the slogan: “no settlement in Tunisia.” This intersects with xenophobic sentiments in the public opinion, as well as xenophobic violence (Boubakri, synthesis workshop 12 December 2024). Being stuck in these harsh living circumstances creates a demand among sub-Saharan African migrants to return to their origin country.

Once they reach out to IOM, people are often in urgent need of resources, medical and food assistance, and accommodation. The IOM, funded through the €1 billion EU-Tunisia deal to stem irregular migration, provides the infrastructure for migrants to return.

In collaboration with the government of Tunisia and the Tunisian Red Crescent and in coordination with IOM offices in the countries of origin and IOM regional offices, 3,500 sub-Saharan African migrants were returned through AVRR between January 1 and June 25, 2024 (IOM 2024a). Such AVRR was made possible through the European Union Migrant Protection, Return and Reintegration in North Africa (MPRR-NA) programme (IOM 2023a). This program is supposed to provide pre-departure and post-arrival services, including free return flights for migrants, and help their reintegration into their home countries (IOM 2024b; TRT Africa 2024). However, many of the migrants do not get the chance to access the programme as the procedures are done haphazardly, following arrest and later expulsion

(Source: Nigeria Country Dossier)

3. **Deportation** – indicates all forms of physically forced return – is in line with Şahin-Mencütek & Triandafyllidou’s (2025) ‘imposing’ of returns. This includes arrest, detention, and armed escort across the border and comes with (the threat of) physical violence. Deportation can both be used as an actual instrument to physically remove irregularized humanitarian migrants, but also as a threat that induces self-return. Considering the cost of deportation, this latter aspect often becomes the focus, meaning that deportations take place in relatively small numbers that are made highly visible through media coverage.

Box 3: Deportations from Lebanon to Syria

Syrian refugees in Lebanon can be forcibly returned by the General Security Office responsible for migration management on two grounds: for illegal entry or presence and for committing criminal offenses seen to pose a threat to national security. Considering the fact that in 2024 only 20 percent of Syrian refugees in Lebanon had legal residency status and that it is notoriously hard to renew or obtain such a residency, by far the largest number of Syrians in Lebanon is therefore in theory. In practice, it is mostly those refugees arrested at checkpoints, at instances of paper renewal, or through raids, or those reported by others that are actually arrested. Syrians are often deported without going through official procedures or remain in indefinite detention.

In addition to such individual deportations, the Lebanese Armed Forces have been carrying out collective deportations through discriminatory raids in neighbourhoods across Lebanon on the houses of Syrian refugees and deporting them without observing formal procedures. It was reported that during April-May 2023 alone, around 1,800 people were deported in this way. These were, according to Human Rights Watch, summary deportations: “after the raids people would find themselves on the borders without being informed they were being deported” (Syria Direct 2023). Al Jazeera (2023) reports that such irregular deportations, which have at times left minors separated from their families, have caused widespread fear. Experts, moreover, estimate that hundreds more people have been sent back to Syria, through ad-hoc deportations before and after this peak moment. Various people deported were subsequently arrested and detained by Syrian security agencies, leading rights organizations to conclude that such deportations could breach Lebanon’s non-refoulement obligations.

Deportations are thus highly informalized and securitized, occurring through an ad hoc process defined by extensive arbitrariness and discretionary power of the security agencies involved in deportation. Indeed, considering that many people returned from Lebanon to Syria re-enter Lebanon soon after, it is precisely the fear generated by such widespread and arbitrary deportation risks that in turn might spur self-return that appears to be the main governance function of deportation.

(Source: Lebanon Country Dossier)

4. **Pushbacks** – resonating with Şahin-Mencütek & Triandafyllidou’s (2025) ‘pushing returns’ – refer to enforced non-entrée, supposedly before crossing international borders, but also often including summary deportations from border zones or ‘no-man’s-land.’ While states have the sovereign right to be selective in allowing entry to their territory, they also have obligations under international law to allow people to claim asylum and protection, something pushbacks prevent.

Box 4: Pushbacks from Turkey to Iran

Pushbacks of Afghans at Turkey’s eastern border with Iran have been common ever since the Taliban took over Afghanistan in 2021 and many Afghan people sought to enter Turkey via Iran. Such pushback practices have increased significantly since 2022 and now constitute the most common type of return for Afghan humanitarian migrants.

A lawyer from Van, a major Turkish border town, observed: “Afghans are deported almost immediately; they are push backs. There is no time for them to apply for asylum or even understand what is happening.”ⁱ This, according to an interlocutor from Van, means that, “when migrants are caught at the border, they are often immediately sent back to Iran without official documentation, bypassing any formal return process.”ⁱⁱ There are documented cases where migrants are “...stripped and forced to cross back into Iran during the winter, with many risking hypothermia.”ⁱⁱⁱ

Such pushbacks constitute a central practice in Turkey’s return migration governance towards Afghan people. In April 2022, Turkey completed a 191 km-long wall at the border with Iran and announced that it would be extended to 295 km by 2023 (Hurriyet 2022). This border fortification was enabled by the EU through over a hundred million Euros in financial support.^{iv} Reports present informal directives of the national police instructing border guards to push back migrants seeking to enter the country via the border with Iran in order to avoid the costs involved in legally processing asylum claims and hosting humanitarian migrants. A field expert similarly concludes: “It’s state-organized pushback now. [...] It’s not like before; it’s now an official mechanism.”^v The governor of Van confirmed this, stating that nearly 120,000 migrants had been blocked from entering via the Van border in 2021 alone (Dalmaz 2021). Turkish migration authorities estimate the total number of intercepted irregular migrants at 2,737,732 between 2016 and 2022. After being returned to Iran, they were often subsequently deported to Afghanistan (PMM 2022).

Documenting pushbacks is particularly hard because of the informal nature of this return type that occurs directly at the border, to which monitoring organizations often hardly have access. An EU representative admitted that “there are gaps in how we monitor forced returns, particularly in the east where Afghans are most vulnerable.”^{vi}

(Source: Turkey Country Dossier)

Scale of returns (and the politics of statistics)

“[The] hidden aspect of migration underscores the scale of movement that remains undocumented, complicating efforts to manage and monitor returns effectively.” (Libya Country Dossier).

Reliable statistics on coerced returns are not self-evident. The table below shows a rough and relative estimate of return numbers of the past five years for each host country and country of origin, as well as the main return migration strategies per host country.

Table 1: Scale of return and main return migration types* per host country

	Estimated total return (2020-2024)	Self-Return	Assisted Return	Deportation
Lebanon To Syria	40.000-70.000 (UNHCR, 2024b)	+++	+	++
Jordan To Syria	25.000	+++	-	+
Iraq to Syria	20.000	+++	+	++
Turkey To Syria	120.000-200.000 (PMM 2025)	+++	+	++ (Claude Artifact 2024)
Turkey to Afghanistan	370.000 - 442,505 (AHaber 2024)	+	+	+++ (Human Rights Watch 2022)
Iran to Afghanistan	5,400.000 (UNHCR 2020, 2021, 2023b, 2024a/b)	+++ (UNHCR 2024b)	+	++ (UNHCR 2024b)
Libya to Nigeria	10,000**	+++	+	-
Morocco to Nigeria	2,000**	+++	+	-
Tunisia to Nigeria	1,000**	-	+	-

*Main return migration types are presented as estimations in relative sense (and does not represent absolute numbers): +++: *most* returnees via this type of return; +: *least* returnees via this type of return. The category ‘pushbacks’ is omitted in this table due to the lack of formal data on this form of return. However, this absence of information is itself telling, as the opaqueness is often deliberately maintained.

**Very rough estimates of assisted returns only. Accurate data on Nigerian returns from Libya, Morocco, and Tunisia is limited. Available figures from the IOM cover only assisted returns through the AVRR and VHR programmes, which facilitated the return of 34,491 Nigerians between 2017 and 2023. During this period, 60,162 individuals (not merely Nigerians) were returned from Libya, 11,657 from Morocco, and 5,748 from Tunisia. Nigerians made up the largest group of assisted returns from North Africa, accounting for 25% of the total (IOM 2024).

The absence of reliable statistics is a finding as such, indicating: (1) varying administrative or bureaucratic capacities to monitor and register return movement; (2) the political push to either overstate return numbers when they fit populist programmes or understate the types of return, such as deportations and pushbacks, that are contested at best and illegal at worst under international law (Stel 2020), also with an eye to rentier logics (Tsourapas 2019). For the same reasons, states can strategically avoid producing or sharing such statistics (Natter et al. 2023); and (3) the avoidance of migrants to be registered or monitored by state bodies. As an interviewee in Libya said, “many migrants prefer to stay hidden, knowing the risks of being identified and detained” (Libya country dossier). This shows the precarity of migrants on one

hand and the many different political stakes on the other (see the section on interests of return migration governance below).

Return governance actors

This section explores the different actors on different scales of governance that are involved in various types of return: inter/supra-governmental; governmental/state; private; and civil society. While the country dossiers present the often-complex web of actors (Olakpe 2020), we here draw out general patterns across cases with a specific focus on state actors, ‘the main actors who have full authority over returning or not returning people,’ and international organizations, who ‘have been particularly active in the last 20 years in promoting and shaping both the discourse and the policy of returns’ (Şahin-Mencütek et. al. 2023, 6, 7; see also Ahouga 2024). (The role of the EU is discussed in a separate section later in the report)

The presence or absence of a designated central state authority to oversee return governance aligns with the general effectiveness of such governance. In Iran, Turkey, Jordan, Iraq and Morocco, return governance is highly centralized through departments of the Ministries of Interior, Security and/or Foreign Affairs.

In cases where the effectiveness of states is lower and the control of migration governance is in practice not with the state, non-state actors become dominant players in the field of return governance. In Libya, while the Libyan Government of National Unity (GNU) nominally oversees migration policy, political fragmentation and the absence of a central state limits the degree of control, and militias manage some detention centres and demand bribes to allow return. Similarly, in Lebanon, Lebanon’s inter-ministerial return committee is practically inactive, and while security agencies (including the army, the Higher Defence Council and the General Security) are identified as the main implementing agencies governing return, political competition between ministries affiliated with different political parties over the return ‘file’ produces fragmentation and deadlock, which results in localization and informalization of return governance. Political parties – which often operate as hybrid actors that have a presence in parliament or government but also operate parallel social and political movements distinct from and sometimes in competition with state institutions (Fakhoury 2021; Stel 2020)– pioneer their own return initiatives parallel to official state policies and practices – in terms of international diplomacy efforts, national policy initiatives and local practices. Also, different local level militias and vigilante groups are involved in repressive practices aimed at enforcing return. Municipal actors are pro-active in repressive measures to encourage return (evictions, curfews, labor restrictions, surveillance and registration).

In many cases, coalitions of civil society actors including local CSOs and (international) NGOs and international protection and rights associations are active to safeguard against imposed returns and are in some cases reported to also contest and question return. In Lebanon, an array of CSOs and NGOs seeks to monitor and contest coerced returns and uphold protection through field interventions and national and international advocacy. In Libya, NGOs cooperate with some detention centres to help with humane treatment. In Iraq, human rights NGOs are contesting deportation to Syria for being unconstitutional.

In all cases the IOM and the ICMPD are crucial and dominant actors in providing operational support to (state) actors wishing to implement return (Younes 2024). In Libya and Tunisia they even seem to be the key drivers of return governance. The IOM manages resettlement processes and is involved in building capacity for or implementing assisted return programs in regional host countries, predominantly Turkey, Morocco, Libya, Tunisia, and more recently,

Iran. ICMPD is particularly active in Turkey where it builds capacity for a ‘national return mechanism. In Nigeria, it plays a crucial role in supporting and promoting sustainable return and reintegration strategies. While the ICMPD formally focuses on assisted return, the people trained, facilities built, and procedures developed also enable enforced return.

Conversely, UNHCR, which formally has a mandate to protect refugees, is often practically unable to uphold this in the tension between normative public positioning on the one hand and practical pragmatism on the other – where the latter seems largely the result of increasingly aligning pressures by host country governments and donor countries. As a result, it mostly takes a monitoring role. In Lebanon, UNHCR is reportedly extremely marginalized and obstructed in its work in the politicized return field, for example by being denied access to detention centres. In the case of Turkey, UNHCR is regarded as a critical ‘normative broker’ between the EU and Turkey in addition to its important (albeit partial) monitoring presence on the ground. Other international rights organizations (such as Human Rights Watch, Amnesty International, and ECRE) are reported to be instrumental in monitoring and advocating for protection.

The EU offers funding for the IOM’s and ICMPD’s operational missions as well as state-level capacity building through various funding schemes (Olakpe 2020). In Libya for example, the IOM’s Voluntary Humanitarian Return (VHR) program, is funded in part by the EU through the Emergency Trust Fund for Africa and its successor programme Neighbourhood, Development and International Cooperation Instrument – Global Europe.

Policies and practices driving return migration governance

In this section, we explore the different decisions and actions that govern different types of return migration. While we recognize that in most settings return initiatives have formal and informal dimensions and any distinction between policy and practice is inherently artificial (Şahin-Mencütek and Triandafyllidou 2025; Stel 2020), in line with our governance approach we nevertheless analytically differentiate between official policy (the laws and decisions recognized on paper by actors formally part of the state) and practice (the actions and initiatives happening ‘on the ground’ that may divert or be separate from such policies). Practices here also include outcomes of formal policies that were not officially stated (i.e. it might be a formal policy to minimize issuing residency permits, which practically functions as a driver for return even if this is not the officially stated purpose of this policy).

With self-return, by far the most significant return type in terms of scale, the underlying governance strategy is irregularization (Stel 2020; Tunaboğlu 2024). Policies and practices that generate such irregularization, which in turn produces the forms of marginalization and exclusion that are meant to push people to self-return, can relate to restrictive entry and residency regulations that incentivize irregular entry and stay. In Iraq, for example, a tightening of the visa regime for Syrian people in Iraq’s Kurdistan region that was demanded by Iraq’s federal government apparently had the aim of pushing people to leave. Such irregularization at times is enabled by non-registration, which can be strategic – as we saw in Lebanon where the government prohibited UNHCR to continue refugee registration to minimize refugee protection so as to discourage new arrivals and push for returns. In Turkey, Refugee Status Determination (RSD) falls under the Presidency of Migration Management

(PMM). The number of successful asylum applications for non-Syrians drastically declined since 2018.

Active or passive irregularization in turn often undercuts people's access to services and livelihoods and hampers their mobility in ways that 'encourage' return. Here we see a general paradigm shift from focusing on inclusion, socio-economically but also in terms of eligibility for asylum or other protection mechanisms, to focusing on exclusion, socio-economically and territorially. The degree to which formal entry and residency policies are actually implemented in reality – through practices such as controlling irregular border crossings, installing checkpoints, and overall linking employment, education, freedom of movement, and access to personal status papers to entry and residency status (as apparent in Iran's Amayesh system of precarious refugee registration) – shows the interaction between policy and practice in this regard. In Turkey, for instance, targeted campaigns of 'deconcentration,' address verification and subsequent deactivation of status demonstrate a practical follow-up of related policies. In Lebanon, practices implementing stringent residency policy were rather used as ad hoc controls of Syrian businesses and homes.

The precarious, unpredictable, uncertain, and conditional nature of the residency status that determines people's access to services, livelihoods, and mobility tends to push people to self-return. In addition to the actual exclusion from work, education, and health care, the constant threat that such exclusion may come about operates as a significant push factor for premature return. This also means that practice can move beyond the administrative into the domain of the political and popular, where political campaigns of xenophobia are translated to the 'streets' in the form of social exclusion and even assaults on humanitarian migrants with the aim to force them to leave the country – as we saw in for instance Lebanon, Tunisia and Turkey. Turkey's cross-border military operations to create 'safe zones' inside Syria to some extent also amount to a push for self-return. In a context of increasingly hostile rhetoric towards Syrians, Syrian people in Turkey are pressured to self-return to these areas. In Tunisia, the president's anti-migrant rhetoric and subsequent xenophobia pushed migrants to leave. In Libya we see other forms of direct physical violence and torture being leveraged to not merely exploit and extort people but also to expel them through self-return.

Self-return can also come about through more constructive strategies, where policies and practices focus on opening border crossings or creating a wide array of modalities to encourage temporary return, which are often meant to prefigure longer-term or permanent return – such as Jordan's 'visitor permits' and Turkey's visas for 'go-and-see-visits' around religious holidays. In Iran, investments in advertising life opportunities in Afghanistan are another example of encouraging premature return. Overall, however, self-return appears the preferred governance strategy to bring about return. This is because it keeps up a semblance of voluntariness, which a host state needs to protect itself against allegations of refolement, and because it is in many instances the 'cheapest' way to generate return.

Assisted return, a type of return much smaller in scale than self-return, comes about through various programs and projects, often institutionally or financially supported by foreign donors. The degree to which these assisted return programs are stand-alone initiatives or embedded in more extensive legal or policy frameworks varies widely per country. The scope and nature of assisted return programs also differs for different countries. In Lebanon, General Security, responsible for immigration matters, independently runs what it calls a facilitated group return program for which Syrian people can register. Once sufficient people have indicated interest, General Security checks bilaterally with Syrian security agencies

whether registered people would face any security threats upon return to Syria. Only people 'cleared' after this procedure are then escorted to the border where remaining fees are waived and departure is administratively handled. UNHCR is nominally present to observe the voluntary nature of these assisted returns. This state-run program followed several more informal initiatives along the same lines that were set up by various Lebanese political parties that had good relations with the Syrian regime.

Lebanon's direct bilateral form of assisted return seems an outlier, however, as most forms of assisted return we studied were developed by or through international organizations. In Turkey, assisted return is under the authority of PMM and enabled by extensive capacity-building of IOM and ICMPD. In Libya, the IOM runs a humanitarian return program. In Morocco, the IOM also started assisted returns after a memorandum of understanding was concluded with the government in 2005. In Iran, we saw assisted return through a tripartite agreement established in 1992 and revised in 2000.

Throughout our case studies, assisted return appears to be the preferred return modality by the international actors with which host country authorities collaborate (and on whom they are often dependent in various ways), but remains very small in numbers. Although all the strategic push factors discussed in relation to the self-return strategies above also hold here, the impression of not merely voluntariness but also international legitimacy makes this return type a (geo-)politically expedient return strategy even if it remains modest in scale.

With deportation, the gap between policy and practice appears most striking. While in almost all settings deportations are formally conditional on various legal standards and due process regulations, in practice they are often implemented without respecting many or most of these checks and balances. A returning feature of deportations, then, is that return governance actors often appear to legally justify these forced returns but that legal protections against forced return are simultaneously disregarded on a large scale – although, as noted, before, the scale of deportation is hard to determine precisely because of its often informal implementation.

In Lebanon, deportation is officially conditional on a legal deportation order which can only come about after a due process in which people should be heard on any security concerns related to return and in which UNHCR should be able to intervene. In practice, many deportations do not observe such due process. Recent years have seen various campaigns of summary deportation which are often legitimized with reference to a classified decision by the country's Higher Defence Council decision from 2019 that legal experts deem unconstitutional. In other countries, even in settings like Jordan and Iraq where the political context has been less hostile for humanitarian migrants, we have seen similar bouts of deportation – with around 2000 people being deported from Jordan in 2017 and tens of people in Iraq in 2024 (despite a law banning such deportation being adopted the year before).

The common denominator here is a reference to often undivulged security threats (Şahin-Mencütek 2023). With reference to national security or terrorism, the security agencies involved in deportation legally obtain extensive discretionary power that – at least in their reading – allows them to bypass most of not all of the due process considerations usually in place with formal deportation procedures. The same securitization means information about the number and nature of such deportations is often not publicly available as access to deportation centres or border crossings is elusive for monitoring organizations and data on deportations is kept classified. Where deportations do become public, this often regards

collective deportations, where a large number of people are deported at once. Individual deportations, which according to interviewed experts often account for many more people, more often remain under the radar.

We also note that the classification of humanitarian migrants as either refugees or migrants can have severe consequences for their being targeted for deportation. In Turkey, both Syrian and Afghan people face deportation threats, but these play out on a different scale and in a different way. Regarding Syrian refugees, Turkey appears keen to uphold the pretence of voluntariness – even coercing people to sign voluntary return forms. Concerns for voluntariness do not apply in the same way to Afghans, who are mainly considered irregular migrants in Turkey (see context section) and therefore do not even have paper protection from deportation.

The underlying rationale for pushbacks is that people who try to irregularly enter a country – either through an informal border crossing or through using irregular documentation – are prevented from doing so. This is usually legitimized through specific entry policies that stipulate who can enter the country under what conditions and enables authorities to bar ‘unwanted’ entries with reference to sovereignty. Such non-entrée policies are implemented through formal border control mechanisms, where people are ‘intercepted’ at the border at both official and unofficial crossings, as well as targeted ‘anti-smuggling’ operations against the actors facilitating irregular entry – as with Turkey’s cross-border military operations. Fortification of borders – like Turkey’s elaborate construction of border walls – can also be considered a practice that facilitates pushback.

With pushbacks, too, distinctions between refugees and other migrants have a significant impact. Where pushing back refugees is often at odds with obligations under humanitarian or refugee law, this is not considered the case for other humanitarian migrants. This also means that while preventing the entry of migrants is often publicly claimed as successful border management, pushing back people considered (potential) refugees is often less blatant, even where it happens systematically. A further complicating matter is that in some cases borders are less clearly demarcated than often assumed. This means that it is not always clear whether people apprehended in border zones and then forcefully returned have or have not already crossed the border. For authorities, it is politically expedient to claim they have not and that their return, therefore, is a case of pushback – a return type considered legitimate and practised widely by all state authorities, also those in the Global North – rather than acknowledge that they had crossed the border and their ‘pushback’ thus actually constitutes deportation – which, as discussed above, is formally subject to more extensive due process. Because international organizations and rights groups often have limited access to border zones and people are subjected to pushbacks and deportations there such distinctions, however, remain elusive.

Driving forces of return migration governance in the African and Middle Eastern regions

Historically, the host countries under study often did not feel the need to heavily enforce return. Yet, in the past decade they have all joined the global ‘return turn,’ meaning a general move towards a focus on return migration governance, sometimes with an emphasis on specific migrant populations (Olakpe 2020). In this section, we explore why and how this

reorientation towards return migration governance has come about, discussing interests, capacities, and the role of the EU.

Core observations

- While **state narratives** on return highlight the necessity of return by pointing to socio-economic pressures and societal and cultural tensions as well as security threats, analysts point to the **political instrumentalization** of return on a domestic as well as international scale.
- Considerations to push for particular types of return appear to be mostly determined by **historical and geopolitical interests**. Countries with positive historical experiences or currently geopolitically beneficial experiences with hosting humanitarian migrants appeared most likely to refrain from coercing returns. When humanitarian migrants are labelled as refugees, geopolitical **donor dependencies** serve as an interest to highlight return types likely to be perceived as voluntary, such as self-return and assisted return, even if these, as we illustrate throughout this report, are often coerced as well;
- Different return types require and are born out of different **capacities** for return migration governance. Highly capable states can afford to opt for resource-intense return types such as assisted return and deportation, while self-return is the default option for less-capacitated state apparatuses.
- Host states largely depend on international organizations for financial, legal, technological, institutional, and operational support to realize assisted return and deportation. While these international actors often demand **nominal adherence to voluntary return and non-refoulement principles**, the capacity built for assisted returns often extends to deportations.
- The **drivers** of return migration governance in the African and Middle Eastern regions originate from the combined **fortification and externalization** of EU migration management, which has increasingly prevented onward movement or resettlement from regional host countries to the EU.
- This has contributed to heightened host state **interest** to return irregularized humanitarian migrants. The **capacities** to do so have also been crucially informed by the EU, which has at times repurposed development aid and other external policy instruments to both develop states' capacities to close their borders and control migrant populations and enable international organizations to support states in assisted return – support that also capacitates deportations.
- The **characteristics** of return migration governance in the African and Middle Eastern regions are thereby also fundamentally shaped by the EU's external migration policy, such as the preference for assisted return and self-return and the presentation of these modalities as voluntary; the increasing securitization of the actors involved; and the irregularization and marginalization that produce deportability.
- The involvement of the EU, across regions and types of migration, reflects a highly **securitized logic** that allows for secretive, extra-legal non-entrée and return practices that are legitimized with reference to criminalization, terrorism, and national security threats.

Interests driving return migration governance

Different categories of interests surfaced as important drivers of return migration governance in our case-study countries. Interests are here defined in a broad sense as bringing advantages or being important to the state (Leerkes and Van Houte 2020); as the motivations of various actors for governing particular types of return in particular ways.

- **Socio-economic interests** regard instances when actors refer to the need to alleviate pressure on the economy and social infrastructure – such as schools, housing, and healthcare – as a reason to push for return (Müller-Funk, Fröhlich, and Bank 2024).
- **Security interests** relate to instances where return policy or practice is motivated with references to mitigating domestic social and political tensions and criminal and security threats – whether physical or symbolic – including fear of moral degeneration, demographic change, ethnic violence, and terrorism (Fakhoury 2021).
- **Political interests** capture instances where return is justified with reference to electoral logics and/or threats to political norms and procedures. This category of interests also includes disproportional political salience of the presence of particular migrant populations in relation to historical experiences with these populations or the country from which they originate (Içduygu and Nimer 2020; Stel 2020).
- **Geopolitical interests** concern occasions where return governance is motivated with reference to international norms or interests; where, for instance, (the threat of) deportation or onward migration is used as leverage in migration diplomacy towards origin states or potential destination countries. This also includes the interest to maintain or obtain donor funding (Şahin-Mencütek 2023; Şahin-Mencütek and Tsourapas 2023).

Importantly, these different categories of interests all focus on the interest of the host country. Often, return governance actors motivate return policy and practice also with reference to the interests of the humanitarian migrants that are encouraged to return – with the claim that they have better prospects in their country of origin – but since our report findings focus predominantly on host country return governance, in our analysis we focus on the stated interests of the actors involved in return governance themselves.

Furthermore, the interests that are *stated* to drive return may not correspond with the *perceived* interests or motivations of the actors involved; and perceived interests may in turn not reflect *actual* objective interests of these actors. Authorities may publicly promote return for the sake of socio-economic prosperity of citizens, while their back stage strategy is to politically/electorally benefit from such a return agenda. Or return governance actors may think they promote domestic security interests by enforcing return while such premature returns unintendedly exacerbate (regional) security threats.

Finally, although analytically disentangled in the above, these clusters of interests always occur in interaction with each other.

Capacities driving return migration governance

Actors involved in governing return, meaning actors associated with the policies and practices realizing different types of return, may have all kinds of interests to push for return. But that does not mean they can actually realize such returns. This is because humanitarian migrants

themselves often resist coerced return. Various local, national, and international CSOs – including rights groups and migrant-led networks – also work to preempt or condition premature or illegally forced returns. Other actors – sometimes formally or informally associated with the state actors claiming to work for return – may also have vested economic or political interests in maintaining (some categories) of (exploitable) migrants and hence prevent return. In addition, many actors involved may not have the resources needed to implement various return initiatives. In discussing the capacities for return, we thus outline what material, financial, and human resources exist to implement particular types of return and where such capacities are located (with which actors and at what scales of governance).

We predominantly focus on the capacities of domestic – mostly state – actors governing return as well as the ways in which their capacities are bolstered by external/international actors. In terms of state return capacity, variations in the overall administrative and executive capacities of the state apparatus also crucially shape return governance. Where such capacity is limited, as in Lebanon and Libya, we will see different types and scales of return – generally smaller scale return that is more focused on self-return – than where such capacity is more profound, as in Jordan and Iran, or even strong, as in Turkey – where return happens at a relatively larger scale and self-return is meaningfully complemented by assisted return and deportation.

In the below table, we present an overview of the core interests and capacities driving return migration governance as presented in the respective country dossiers.

Table 2: Country-level (state) return interests and capacities

Host state	Interests	Capacities
Lebanon	<p>Lebanese state actors predominantly present ambitions to alleviate <i>financial and economic</i> burdens and mitigate <i>social</i> tensions as the interests driving their return migration agenda.</p> <p><i>Political</i> scapegoating and <i>electoral</i> opportunism as well as <i>trauma</i> with previous refugee presences may be equally or more important interests underpinning the incentivization of return.</p> <p>While these interests drive a general return agenda – independent of different types – interests to maintain <i>donor funding</i> might incentivize types of return that can be presented as voluntary.</p>	<p>Characterized by financial crises and institutional deadlock, Lebanese state actors have <i>limited capacity to organize assisted return and deportation</i>. Donor support for various security agencies involved in border control does increase deportation and pushback capacity.</p> <p>Through passive irregularization and marginalization, Lebanon does have the <i>capacity to push for self-return</i>. In addition, Lebanon’s highly capable political parties that to different degrees operate as parallel return governance actors also have relevant capacity to extend informal, local practices of exclusion and marginalization.</p>
Jordan	<p>Jordanian state actors present ambitions to alleviate <i>financial and economic</i> burdens and mitigate <i>social</i> tensions as their main motivation to encourage future return.</p> <p>Historical <i>legacies</i> of refugee reception and interests to maintain international reputation and donor funding weigh in heavily to incentivize the <i>voluntary</i> – and therefore so far largely suspended – nature of such return.</p>	<p>Jordanian state capacity to organize or enforce return was assessed as adequate for small-scale returns, but not for extensive return.</p> <p>In preparing for future voluntary return on a larger scale, Jordan seems to have predominantly invested in its <i>regional diplomacy capacity</i> to try and incentivize Syrian authorities to facilitate return.</p>

Turkey	<p>Turkish state representatives predominantly present <i>financial and economic</i> burdens and <i>social</i> tensions and <i>security</i> concerns as the reasons that spur their return migration agenda.</p> <p><i>Political</i> scapegoating and the related <i>electoral</i> opportunism as well as perceived <i>security</i> threats are considered by interviewed experts as important unstated interests underpinning Turkish return migration governance.</p> <p>Interests to maintain <i>donor funding</i> incentivize Turkish state actors to prioritize types of return that can be presented as voluntary.</p>	<p>State actors in Turkey have ample administrative and executive capacity on all governance scales. This is corroborated by the <i>diplomatic</i> capacity to pressure Syrian counterparts and the <i>military</i> capacity to create return zones on Syrian territory.</p> <p>Institutional collaboration with and funding for migration management from the EU (through IOM, ICMPD, and UNHCR) crucially underpins this state's capacity. These capacities are formally directed at <i>assisted return</i>, but de facto sustain an extensive <i>deportation</i> regime.</p>
Iraq	<p><i>Political and electoral</i> interests shape Iraq's return governance on two scales. Whereas Iraq's Kurdistan Region has long sought to welcome Syrian Kurds and prevent return in order to boost its population, the federal Iraqi government does not want more Kurdish people to settle in the Kurdistan region, likely for fear of bolstering independence aspirations, and therefore has an interest in return to Syria.</p> <p><i>Socio-economic</i> interests in the form of increasing labor market competition, however, have increasingly driven actors in the Kurdistan Region of Iraq to be less resistant to federal return interests.</p>	<p>Iraq is one of the few countries that has a designated ministry for migration and displacement which develops return programs and aims to facilitate their implementation. Yet, at the time of writing, Iraq's return capacities rely on a weak legal framework, overstretched detention facilities, and limited international funding.</p> <p>While voluntary return is prioritized, deportation remains an option under the Foreigners' Residency Law No. 76 of 2017, particularly for cases framed as security threats. The EU-Iraq Partnership and Cooperation Agreement (2012) strengthens return capacities by promoting cooperation on migration management, readmission, and voluntary return under humane conditions (Warda et al. 2020).</p>
Iran	<p>For Iranian return governance actors, deportation threats serve as a <i>geopolitical tool</i> to gain political leverage and manage disputes with Afghanistan. Additionally, minimal access to international donor funds and the UN refugee hosting system further incentivizes efforts to push for return.</p> <p>As a <i>foreign policy tool</i>, return migration has played a key role in Iran's bilateral disputes, particularly in settling water conflicts and supporting Shia minorities, including Hazaras and Tajiks.</p> <p><i>Socio-economically</i> and <i>historically</i>, there is a stated interest to diminish the pressures on state services and the tensions between Afghan and Iranian communities that are generated by a large influx of Afghans in a short time, on top of an existing refugee population.</p>	<p>Iran's initial open-door policy was partly related to the absence of an institutional framework to manage migration. Over time, this migration management capacity has grown and adapted to the circumstances. Iran's enforcement capacity seems focused on administering social exclusion mechanisms and political/mediatized pressure fostering <i>self-return</i>, and less on actual deportation actions.</p>
Libya	<p>Libya's government and local power structures arguably prioritize return migration governance as part of their broader national <i>security</i> and <i>socio-economic</i> strategies since the presence of large migrant populations in</p>	<p>The lack of a central state in Libya severely limits migration governance capacity, also for return. Strategic non-regulation, where selective inaction and ambiguous enforcement create an environment of</p>

	Libya is perceived to place pressure on already fragile political and economic systems.	controlled unpredictability, does operate to push for <i>self-return</i> .
Morocco	<p>As a result of <i>diplomatic and geopolitical</i> pressure from the EU, Morocco, historically uninterested to control the EU's borders, has shifted from transit to a containment-oriented migration governance. As a result of that, increased <i>socio-economic</i> pressure on employment, education, and infrastructure and social tensions are presented as interests to push for return.</p> <p>At the same time, Morocco has a competing <i>regional geopolitical</i> interest to maintain good relations with Nigeria and the African Union with an eye to its territorial conflict with Spain, which comes with interests to prevent <i>forced returns</i>.</p>	Morocco's return migration governance entails a substantive legal framework, a multi-faceted institutional infrastructure, and a range of AVRR programs, supported by the IOM and particularly aimed at Francophone, Sub-Sahara Africans. Laws 02-03 and 27-14 provide the legal framework for managing the entry, stay, and return of migrants. Bilateral agreements with several European countries and EU-funded AVRR programs form the bedrock of Morocco's state capacity facilitating return.
Tunisia	Tunisian state actors primarily stress the need to reduce <i>economic</i> pressures and <i>social</i> instability. Sub-Saharan migrants are <i>politically</i> framed as a security concern, feeding populist tensions and fueling the country's return agenda. Also <i>geopolitical interests</i> , including adhering to EU pressure to control migration to secure donor funding, play a significant role. Tunisia's position as a transit hub for Sub-Saharan migrants puts pressure to align with EU priorities such as strengthened border controls and stricter migration policies.	Tunisia has limited state capacity to enforce return migration due to outdated <i>legislation</i> and <i>financial</i> constraints. Therefore, Tunisia's return capacities are bolstered by international organizations, predominantly IOM, and bilateral agreements with several European countries. Its reliance on external funding highlights domestic capacity gaps.

Role of the EU

"The EU has closed its doors, while simultaneously encouraging our states to close the doors for others" (Hassen Boubakri, Synthesis workshop, 12 December 2024)

"The role of the EU as a driving force in return migration governance is pronounced. Through financial aid and policy agreements, the EU has shaped Libya's migration management landscape" (Libya country dossier)

In this section, we address a crucial dimension of all of our three main questions: how do EU policy and politics impact the drivers – defined as core actors' capacities and interests – of regional return migration governance and thereby the characteristics and consequences of such regional migration governance; how do the normative commitments and geopolitical interests of the EU and its member states as expressed in foreign policy at large and external migration policy more precisely shape the return migration governance of the countries central to this report?

EU impact on the characteristics and drivers of regional return migration governance

Traditionally states in the neighbourhood of displacement did not necessarily feel the need to enforce return or manage migration to realize such return as they saw themselves as temporary host and/or transit states in a more flexible and fluid mobility landscape. There

was a kind of laissez-faire approach or open-door policy, and in the case of refugees seeking protection (Syrian and Afghan refugees) a default and culturally informed hospitality, supported by international actors including the EU, through funding of refugee protection. In this phase, regional host countries' dependency on European aid worked to incentivize countries to uphold the principles of refugee protection that the EU claimed to value, and the porosity of borders made sure that any overstretching of resources or the labour market led to onward migration.

This laissez-faire hospitality changed in reaction to two interrelated shifts in EU policy with regard to mobility since the early 1990s that imposed on countries a reality of 'transit-turned-host states' (Norman 2020). First, the EU's shift towards increased containment policy.

Box 5: AVRR as migration control – IOM and the EU's role in return to Nigeria

In the case of the North African countries bordering the Mediterranean Sea, the role of the EU is pronounced. By intercepting boats crossing to the EU and pushing them back to Tunisia and Libya, the EU forces migrants into detention, where abuse, enforced immobility, and unbearable conditions make return the least harmful option. This has led to a waterbed effect: as Morocco - under EU pressure - intensified border controls, arrests, and pushbacks, it became a key partner in EU migration management. As a result, migrants are restricted to transit through Morocco and are forced to seek alternative pathways, shifting migration flows to Tunisia and Libya and exacerbating pressures there.

The case of Nigerian return migration from North-Africa is exemplary for this tendency. Intensified and externalized border control creates increased demand for return, which the EU subsequently meets by providing operational support in the form of AVRR programs, facilitated by the IOM. While framed as humanitarian assistance, these programs function as a tool for migration control. Also, the use of EU-sponsored biometric enrolment to capture migrants' identities in Mauritania, IOM-facilitated MiDAS technology to monitor migration flows at various borders, risk analysis cells operated by FRONTEX-trained individuals in Niger, and border surveillance at the Melilla border with Morocco are strategies to control people's movements.

By relying on IOM rather than directly funding African governments, the EU exerts control over African (return) migration governance, ensuring that return programs align with its broader strategy while minimizing direct political engagement with national authorities. North African states, benefiting from EU financial support, actively participate by deporting sub-Saharan African migrants and channeling them into these EU-funded return schemes. In this way, EU's restrictive and externalized border policies create a growing demand for return, which it consequently provides through IOM's AVRR programs. This strategy reinforces return migration and moreover shifts the burden of (return) migration governance onto host- and origin countries outside the EU.

Nevertheless, North African states are also increasingly resisting the EU discourse and are using their political leverage they have over the EU: when Germany proposed in 2017 to locally integrate migrants, all North African countries (including Libya, Tunisia, Morocco) refused. In the summer of 2024, Tunisia imposed visa for nationals to enter Tunisia and neighbouring countries.

(Source: Nigeria Country Dossier)

Containment is a complex and longitudinal process that arguably started with the start of the Schengen Agreement (1985) and Convention (1990), which established both free mobility between member states, as well as harmonized border control at its outside borders a continuous process that was part of increasing integration and internalization of European policies into the national (Hassen Boubakri, synthesis workshop). In addition to this internalization process, the EU practices externalization, defined as attempts to convince third states in its neighbourhood to help prevent migrants reaching the EU's borders in exchange for legal mobility arrangements, trade deals, and funding through 'mobility partnerships' or

‘migration deals.’ This EU containment policy of internalization and externalization helped to create congestion of migrants in countries in the region, where migrants got stranded because of a lack of onward options, and return was considered unviable.

Box 6: Chain deportation – the EU’s role in return to Afghanistan

A significant number of individuals classified as returnees from Iran to Afghanistan are, in reality, not actual returnees from Iran but rather pushbacks or deportees from Turkey or even from Europe. Pushbacks from Greece and Bulgaria to Turkey often lead to further pushbacks to Iran and eventual deportation to Afghanistan. One of the main drivers of return migration governance from Iran to Afghanistan is the pushback chain from the EU to Turkey and Turkey to Iran.

Turkey has recently become a country of destination for thousands of irregular migrants from neighboring countries as well as from wider regions, fleeing conflict, war-related hardships, or environmental constraints. While European countries officially suspended the return of rejected Afghan asylum seekers to Afghanistan after the Taliban took over control in August 2021, Turkey continues to return migrants to Afghanistan. Between January and April 2024, over 21,000 Afghans were apprehended by Turkish law enforcement agencies (PMM 2025). Alongside self-returns by charter airlines operating from various provinces in Turkey to Afghanistan, there have also been hundreds of thousands of Afghan pushback incidents from Turkey to Iran. Deportation numbers vary drastically: 200,000 Afghans were deported in 2019 (Deutsche Welle 2020), compared to 20,260 in 2023. In-depth interviews with Afghan returnees further reveal that a significant number of these individuals were indeed deported from EU countries to Turkey before being returned to Afghanistan.

This underscores the indirect but substantial role of the EU in driving Afghan return trajectories. While the EU does not directly dictate strategies to return Afghan migrants, it exerts influence through financial support channelled via international migration agencies in Iran and Turkey such as the IOM, the ICMPD, and UNHCR. With this indirect involvement, EU member states have made substantial contributions to return migration governance in Turkey and Iran. In other words, financial assistance provided by EU member states facilitates the implementation of initiatives to manage and support the return of Afghan migrants, thus exerting a tangible influence on the broader landscape of migration governance in the region. This is exemplified by EU member states like Sweden, Norway, Finland, and Belgium which are key financial contributors to initiatives such as resettlement, pre-departure medical screening programs, AVRR schemes, and the IOM-led Academy for Migration and Refugee Studies in Iran. This chain of deportation spans a wide geographical area and persisted for over a decade, fueling many Afghans to report to self-return and repeatedly moving back- and forth between different destinations.

In 2024, an estimated 1.3 million Afghans either returned or were deported from Iran to Afghanistan (UNHCR 2024a, 7), where mainly three types of return migration become most apparent. On the one hand we see self-return or assisted return of Afghans who hold refugee ID (Amayesh) cards, but are subject to legal precarity, continuous political, socio-cultural, economic pressures, and mediatized marginalization. On the other hand, many Afghans face chain deportation, where Iran deports individuals who have not lived in the country but were previously expelled from Turkey or Europe, continuing the chain of displacement ultimately back to Afghanistan. However, despite these efforts to return, out-migration from Afghanistan still far exceeds the number of returnees, making current return migration governance ineffective.

(Source: Iran Country Dossier)

Second, on top of the congestion in regional host states, and on top of traditionally low resettlement numbers, the EU’s interest to protect refugees, and by extension fund refugee protection in the region, significantly decreased. This had the unintended effect of onward migration to other countries, including the EU. Because of the hardened outer borders of the EU and the lack of regular ways to enter, a crisis situation emerged in which refugees and other migrants risked their lives to try to reach the EU. In response to this so-called ‘European

refugee crisis’, the EU in some cases started to redirect funds in the region to support local refugee ‘absorption’ (see examples in the boxes).

This created congestion in countries in the neighbourhood of displacement on the one hand and lack of funding for local protection or willingness of burden sharing on the other. This in turn undermined regional host country interest to continue ‘bearing the burden’ of humanitarian migrants and helped fuel resistance against the local integration discourse of the EU and a ‘demand’ for return governance in formerly host and transit states – a demand these states in many instances sought to cater to with the support of the very entity creating such demands: the EU. For example, Jordan, Lebanon, Iraq and Turkey are increasingly vocal in their demands that the EU should relocate their funding for Syrian refugees to projects inside Syria so as to incentivize return. This illustrates an unintended consequence of the EU’s ‘spillover’ of externalization (Şahin-Mencütek 2024b), namely the mutual power game, in which the EU’s reliance on the containment role of the states under study also implies that these states have leverage over the EU (Şahin-Mencütek and Tsourapas 2023).

The EU responded to this demand with operational power: funding and capacity building for border management, through intergovernmental organizations such as UNHCR, IOM, and ICMPD, which helped set up AVRR programmes, detention centers, and infrastructures. This regards preventing onward movement, avoiding irregular entry, and facilitating assisted return, but also entails building the capacity of the same actors involved in deportations and pushbacks (and potential refoulement).

The crossover from legal to – according to international and human rights law – illegal ways of border management in some cases followed suit. The impact of the EU on Turkish migration management, for instance, has become increasingly covert and now operates largely via ICMPD with the aim to build capacity for a ‘national return mechanism’ in Turkey. EU-funded facilities like “reception centres” were reoriented toward deportation and the EU enabled integration of administrative systems which has streamlined Turkey’s ability to execute deportations, especially for populations facing precarious circumstances in their home countries, such as Syrians and Afghans (Turkey country dossier).

Another unintended effect is what we may call chain externalization, the phenomenon that host states under study are at times partially copy-pasting and further developing the EU’s and intergovernmental organizations’ policy logics, discourses, and practices (see Turkish case). This includes chain deportation, defined as the subsequent deportation of migrants deported from the EU. And also replicating the normative framework and policies, and contextualizing and reinterpreting them for its own implementation. For example, the creation of deportability through multifaceted irregularization that we see in Lebanon and, to a lesser extent, Iraq and Turkey reflects similar logics in European settings, most notably Denmark.

Box 7: The EU and return migration governance to Syria – containment-through-return-deals

Before the fall of the regime in December 2024, the EU officially considered conditions in Syria un conducive for return and thus did not support or facilitate return. At the same time, the more outspoken Syria's neighbouring countries became about the untenability of their hosting and wanting to return refugees to Syria, the more the EU's containment interests and its formal position on return to Syria became irreconcilable. As a consequence, different EU member states increasingly argued for revisiting the EU's official position on refugee return to Syria and reconsidering the possibility of supporting return. This has also affected the EU's migration 'agreements' with its regional 'partners.' The EU-Turkey and EU-Lebanon 'deals' are no longer just about the EU financing containment in the form of temporary regional hosting but also entail informal EU condoning of coerced return to maintain prevention of onward movement of Syrian people.

The 2016 EU-Turkey Statement institutionalized a logic through which Turkey would prevent onward movement to the EU in exchange for generous European funding for hosting Syrian refugees and developing border and migration management capacity. Considering that the agreement also allowed the EU to return irregular migrants that did arrive in Europe, this deal initially operated under the assumption that Turkey was a 'safe third country' that would not forcefully return Syrian people and risk refoulement – thereby implicating the EU in chain refoulement. As shown in the respective country dossier and this synthesis report, however, not much is left of this initial premise. Turkey is involved in various types of coerced return and the EU appears to by and large turn a blind eye to this reality to uphold containment. What is more, since the capacity to coerce premature return is to a significant extent built through European funding and training via IOM and ICMPD, analysts have argued that the EU directly enables premature coerced return to Syria (Weise et al 2024).

The 2024 EU migration support package for Lebanon centered on implicit EU condonement of premature return from regional host countries. In the bilateral negotiations between Lebanon and Cyprus that preceded this EU 'deal,' Lebanon indicated that to halt ongoing peaks in irregular migration to Cyprus – and hence the EU – it needed not merely more support for border control, but also an acknowledgement that parts of Syria were safe for refugee return. It thereby suggested that less onward movement to Cyprus would depend on more facilitation of return to Syria. While the eventual statement by Von der Leyen that announced the aid package did not explicitly state that Syria or parts of it were safe for return, it did promise that the EU would explore 'how to work on a more structured approach to voluntary returns to Syria, in close cooperation with UNHCR' and indicated that 'there needs to be strengthened support from the international community, for humanitarian and early recovery programs in Syria' (European Commission, 2024). This was seen to signal a softening of the EU's official position that there can be no support for refugee return under the Assad regime and was likely interpreted by Lebanese authorities as tacit green light for their coerced return.

(Source: Lebanon and Turkey Country Dossier)

Consequences of Return Migration Governance in the African and Middle Eastern regions

Having discussed what the main characteristics of return migration governance in the African and Middle Eastern regions are and which drivers can help explain these particular forms of return migration governance and having pinpointed what the role of the EU's external migration policy is in shaping these governance dynamics, this section is concerned with the consequences of the particular forms of return migration management we have identified. We reflect on these consequences in terms of protection, mobility, and diplomacy (Olakpe 2020).

Core observations

- When it comes to protection, our research suggests that in the return migration governance we have discussed above **minimizing protection of humanitarian migrants can be both a consequence and an instrument of return**

governance: on the one hand, undercutting legal and social protection mechanisms is a strategy to push for self-return; on the other hand, increased coerced return migration produces further marginalization and vulnerability. This is reflected in the fact that the more vulnerable migrants are often more likely to be coerced into returning.

- This also follows from the increasingly **blurred boundaries between various return types**. Coerced forms of return migration are then presented as voluntary and thereby escape the scrutiny of under-capacitated monitoring agencies, which further normalizes and institutionalizes coerced return and threatens protection of humanitarian migrants.
- In terms of mobility, the return migration governance dynamics that we see tend to restrict existing circular mobility patterns by **preventing onward migration and trying to limit re-migration or re-entry** after instances of coerced migration.
- With regard to diplomacy, our findings show that **return migration governance can generate multidirectional geopolitical leverage**: origin states may have leverage over host states seeking to return humanitarian migrants through various spoiler mechanisms and conditionalities and host states might influence origin states by imposing or demanding return facilitation through military or socio-economic pressures.

Consequences for protection and (non-)refoulement

The legal dimension of return migration governance entails multiple aspects (Şahin-Mencütek et al. 2023) that are beyond the scope of this working paper. Here, we zoom in on the legal principle of non-refoulement. The principle of non-refoulement is a guiding concern in any case of coerced return since it puts the “strongest restriction on the right to expel derived from international human rights law” (Şahin-Mencütek et al. 2023, 65). We therefore here assess how the characteristics and drivers of return migration governance in the African and Middle Eastern regions, including the role of the EU, that we observed in the previous sections produce pressure on migrants’ protection from refoulement. Do the forms of return migration governance that we see contribute to or undermine the protection of humanitarian migrants in the host country and origin/return country? And do they incentivize or deflect refoulement? While we sketch some generalized patterns here, we refer to Work Packages 7 and 8 of the GAPs project for more insights into the experiences of different categories of humanitarian migrants themselves.

Any type of coerced return migration governance, of any type of migrants, is obliged to adhere to the principle of non-refoulement under the Convention Against Torture (OHCHR 2018). Non-refoulement means that return processes should include a due process procedure in which people to be returned have the chance to indicate reasonable fear for their safety upon return and that such concerns should be independently assessed and return should be made conditional on them (OHCHR 2018).

When reflecting on the humanitarian and legal consequences of the governance of return migration as presented in the country dossiers underpinning this synthesis report, several broad patterns emerge. First, pushing for self-return through policies and practices of legal and socio-economic exclusion appears to be the main return governance strategy in all contexts studied (despite huge divergence between countries in the extent to and ways in which this is pursued). This means that minimizing protection is itself a key return practice across different host country contexts.

When it comes to Syrian humanitarian migrants, we see the tendency to minimize protection specifically in Lebanon, but also in Turkey. In seeking to encourage voluntary return, state actors aim to persuade Syria and international donors to assuage return impediments or create ‘pull factors’ in Syria. But, as we have seen in the above, in some settings they also aim to discourage further stay by de facto socio-economic marginalization and criminalization. This is not always explicitly stated in policy but regularly pursued through practice.

For Afghans, we see even more stringent marginalization to push return in both Turkey and Iran, where stripping humanitarian migrants of legal protection and livelihoods to encourage self-return seems the main return governance modality as well. This underlines once more how within displaced populations it is precisely the most vulnerable people who see no other choice but to return while more affluent people are better protected from legal and socio-economic marginalization or might opt for onward migration. This observation is further illustrated in the context of Nigerian humanitarian migrants. The vulnerability imposed on migrants in Morocco, for instance, comes about through socio-economic marginalization policies and practices. Many people self-return less than two years after arrival in Morocco because of such vulnerabilities.

A second overarching observation emerging from the country dossiers is that it is precisely the overlap and blurring between different return types, specifically between return types usually considered voluntary (which we discuss as self-return and assisted return) and those that are more explicitly forced (deportation and pushback), that further exacerbates protection concerns. This is particularly relevant since such ambivalence is often deliberately generated or maintained by return governance actors (Stel, 2020). In Lebanon and Turkey, for instance, governance actors often deny the coerced nature of self-return and assisted return. They sometimes seek to pass off de facto deportations as assisted return or self-return, and hence voluntary, via various practices – such as forced signing of voluntary return forms and sabotaging due process. As protection mandates of international organizations and local rights groups often focus on monitoring and assuaging deportations and pushbacks, there is a risk that the bulk of returns that are framed as voluntary but are de facto coerced fall off the radar of already overburdened protection agencies and watchdogs.

This also becomes apparent in our own research, which, as we have noted in our discussion on the scale of different return types above, has faced a remarkable lack of reliable statistical and contextual information on all types of return across almost all settings. The more coercive return types become, the more elusive data becomes. While authorities often share numbers on self-return and assisted return, deportation figures and information about deportation processes are often hard to come by. This means that while for most of the settings studied in our Work Package there are ample reports outlining human rights violations, a comprehensive overview of the scale and systematicity of such violations is hard to compose due to the restrictions and repression that monitoring organizations face. Such organizations often have constrained relations with host state governments and face severe constraints in access to return facilities and border zones – and, in the case of Syria and Afghanistan, also to returnees. For Nigerian humanitarian migrants in Libya, to give another example, the severity of human rights violations in detention centres is well-known. How these practices relate to the various types of coerced return, however, is hard to establish and evidence.

This is particularly the case when it comes to refoulement concerns for Syrian refugees. There are authoritative reports detailing various instances of deportation – on a very incidental scale in Jordan and Iraq and more regularly occurring in Lebanon and Turkey – without due process

that would likely meet definitions of refoulement. Yet, because UNHCR and rights organizations do not have systematic access to deportation centres, border zones, and returnees, gauging the exact scope of such practices or formally evidencing such cases is challenging. What we can conclude, therefore, is that the securitization of return migration governance – apparent in the actors involved in return practices and occurring to a different extent in different settings – likely incentivizes refoulement. Such securitization legitimizes enforced returns through criminalization and terrorism charges and allows exceptional and secretive extra-legal practices under the guise of national security. It also justifies limiting the access of monitoring organizations mandated to uphold non-refoulement. The systemic lack of monitoring and data on return institutionalizes impunity. For the EU, its dependence on regional host countries for containment is an incentive to disregard problematic dimensions of regional return governance (Fakhoury and Stel 2023).

Consequences for im/mobility

We here discuss the intended and unintended consequences of return migration governance in the African and Middle Eastern regions, including the role of the EU, on patterns of human mobility. For the diversity of mobility aspirations, experiences and behaviours of different categories of humanitarian migrants themselves, we refer to Work Packages 7 and 8 of the GAPs project.

In the case of mobility within Africa, EU-funded externalization initiatives infringe on cross-border mobility in North and West Africa, which has historically been essential for socioeconomic exchanges and for escaping conflicts. EU-funded technological interventions for border governance disrupt these mobility patterns, partly facilitating migrants' pushback and deportation as they approach Europe's border (Nigeria Country Dossier).

In cases where humanitarian migration follows existing and seasonal labour migration patterns, cross-border mobility is frequent and natural for some migrants and constitutes a coping mechanism when host states maintain an unwelcoming policy. At the same time, such mobility patterns have also undermined the legitimacy of humanitarian migrants as 'real refugees' in the eyes of host country communities and authorities, which in turn has sometimes legitimized premature return practices.

Pressured under (premature) return migration governance, many humanitarian migrants that have the resources resist return and choose onward migration to other countries. For example, in 2023, Syrian people facing increasing return pressures in Lebanon and Turkey opted to relocate to Iraq, where return coercion is less evident. Those who do return often find that the needs driving their initial displacement have not been met and continue to re-emigrate to the same or other countries (Şahin-Mencütek and Triandafyllidou 2025). For example, Syrians deported from Lebanon have subsequently tried to move from Syria to Turkey or Cyprus. Because the regional host countries we discuss here often have direct borders with migrants' origin countries, such cross-border mobility is more likely. This may lead to circular migration in which people tend to re-enter the same host country multiple times.

In many cases, (self-)deportation and assisted return practices have been paralleled with re-entry bans. Considering diverse state capacities and the contestation and navigation by humanitarian migrants (Şahin-Mencütek and Triandafyllidou 2025) this comes with varying results. For example, where Turkey has been relatively effective in preventing re-entries, Lebanon has a much more porous border with Syria and experts estimate that most Syrian people who returned to Syria can re-enter Lebanon. In a similar vein, deportation from Iran

and Turkey to Afghanistan is outnumbered by co-occurring outmigration. For some states, including Jordan and Iraq, the infeasibility of re-entry bans seems to be a crucial reason to abstain from explicitly coercing returns in the first place. In Jordan, the absence of return pressures encourages humanitarian migrants to stay put as onward movement would undermine their resettlement perspectives.

Relatedly, people reportedly face involuntary immobility either after return or in the host country. Involuntarily immobile people face legal and financial obstacles in their desires for mobility. Both involuntarily immobile migrants and returnees get ‘stuck’ in the country in marginalized/precarious conditions including exploitation, extortion and violence. For example in Libya, migrants intercepted at sea or caught within Libya’s borders often face indefinite detention or are forced to remain in precarious conditions without the means to move forward or return home. This has turned Libya into a de facto holding zone. “These states of enforced immobility, entrenched by EU policy, and experiences of violence shape onward migration aspirations, pushing many to seek better protection and stability elsewhere” (Syed Zwick 2022 in Libya Country Dossier).

Although the sustainability of return is often measured by the absence of further mobility, our observations, as well as the wider literature, show that immobility often implies an absence of resources and a level of vulnerability. Our study also shows that the gaps between onward mobility and involuntary immobility suggest an increased inequality in which mobility becomes an unequally divided resource in itself: vulnerable migrants see no choice but to return, while more affluent migrants find ways for re-emigration or onward migration. This is reported in the case of Afghans, where the most vulnerable people see no other choice but to return, and the more affluent people choose onward migration.

Consequences for geopolitics and diplomacy

In this section, we reflect on the ways in which return migration governance in the African and Middle Eastern regions, including the role of the EU, affects bilateral relations between the host and origin country and how it shapes regional geopolitics. See WP5 for a more in-depth analysis of return diplomacy (Adamson and Greenhill 2023; Adamson and Tsourapas 2018; Fakhoury and Şahin-Mencütek 2023; Şahin-Mencütek 2023).

With regard to the bilateral and regional geopolitics and diplomacy involved in return migration, we observe multidirectional power dynamics. On the one hand, on some occasions, origin states have leverage over host states that seek to return humanitarian migrants as they can act as spoilers or set conditions for such return (Şahin-Mencütek and Tsourapas 2023). This we see in the case of Syria, which has largely frustrated the return pushed for by Lebanon and Turkey and has been able to translate the promise of lifting such return sabotage to obtain significant gains in regional diplomacy.

In Lebanon, authorities’ return migration obsessions seem to have produced a renewed leverage of Syria over Lebanon, where promises of enabling return come at the cost of normalizing relations with the Syrian government, something that is sensitive in light of the fact that Syria has held Lebanon politically hostage in other ways between 1976 and 2005. The fact that Iraq was the first to recognize a newly issued Syrian passport, necessary for Syrian people to return to Syria, when Arab League relations with the Syrian regime were still strained also illustrates such Syrian diplomatic influence in the realm of return migration.

Jordan, which has made itself less dependent on immediate and large-scale returns but nevertheless aims to encourage voluntary returns, appears to take a less bilateral approach towards incentivizing Syria to facilitate return than Lebanon and Turkey do. Instead, it has played a leading role in pushing for regional coordination to work towards return. More specifically, in organizing and hosting the May 2023 Amman meeting that paved the way for Syria's re-entry into the Arab League in exchange for, among other things, promises to support return, Jordan has been a driving force in regional return diplomacy. This regional initiative, however, also had a bilateral component in the form of the 'Jordan Initiative,' an initiative that was supposed to serve as a pilot for regional refugee return coordination through which a thousand Syrian refugees would be repatriated from Jordan to Syria. The initiative, however, never materialized as Syria did not appear to honour its part of the Amman bargain.

On the other hand, where origin states are reluctant towards large-scale return or dependent on their diaspora, host states can have leverage over origin states by using the threat of imposed return migration or mistreating humanitarian migrants or by jeopardizing their remittance revenues. In our research, we have seen this in the case of Turkey, whose return ambitions have helped to undercut Syrian sovereignty and to jeopardize the position of the Syrian regime vis-à-vis its main allies. Iran, too, has managed to use return migration as a diplomatic tool in its relations with Afghanistan, where the threat of mass forced return has helped Iran navigate particular political tensions with Afghanistan. Relations between Libya and Nigeria have significantly soured over Libya's inhumane treatment of Nigerian humanitarian migrants.

Morocco has positioned itself, by 2003, as a key partner to the EU in managing irregular migration and human trafficking. Through bilateral agreements (with Spain, France, or Germany, in particular) and cooperation initiatives, it enhances its strategic position in the West-Mediterranean area. The new migration policy it adopted (in 2013) and its adherence to the Global Compact for Safe, Orderly, and Regular Migration (in 2018) allowed it to project the image of a responsible state that values human rights and regional stability. This is despite the fact that it does not have sufficient means to integrate migrants present on its territory in good conditions. This soft power contributes to establishing trust and promoting closer (diplomatic and political) relationships with a series of African partners, such as the countries of the Sahel, from Niger to Senegal, or even Ivory Coast, Nigeria, Ghana, or Cameroon (which represent important areas of departure). These dynamics also appear to affect which return type host countries prioritize. Where host states seeking to return humanitarian migrants think they can pressure origin states into accepting and consolidating explicitly coerced returns they will be more likely to venture beyond pushing for self-return and assisted returns towards deportation.

6. Conclusions

In all contexts studied for this Work Package, this report notes shifts from initial solidarity towards reluctant hosting and increasing return pressure, which is often differentiated across different (strata of) migrant populations. In such settings of protracted displacement, migrants are increasingly made precarious through institutionalization of temporariness and legal and socio-economic exclusion – including intimidation, arbitrary arrests, and violence. As the report shows for different host country settings, this partly results from **the gradual fortification and externalization of EU migration management**. This development has increasingly blocked onward movement or resettlement from regional host countries, undermining their position as transit states. In some ways, this forced them into a more dichotomous policy nexus of integration versus return. The report shows that these dynamics are further complicated by the **multidirectional geopolitical leverage** that return migration governance interactions between neighbouring states produce, where both host and origin states use various geopolitical and diplomatic tools to benefit from either blocking or facilitating return migration.

In such contexts, **marginalization is often instrumentalized to coerce migrants into self-return and facilitated return programs and used to legitimize deportation**. Here, different return types crucially reinforce each other: due to often limited return capacities, resource-intensive return types such as deportation do not merely serve to directly expel targeted migrants, but also to ‘encourage’ self-return, which is less demanding for return actors. Such return actors, the report finds, vary across contexts, ranging from centralized bureaucratic state actors to the dominance of hybrid political actors. **International organizations, often funded by the EU**, play a fundamental role in providing the financial, legal, technological, institutional and operational support that is necessary for assisted returns, but are also found to **build capacities for deportation and pushbacks**. EU support for regional border and migration management, which determines return governance capacities, also has consequences for migrants’ and returnees’ mobility: the resulting migration governance often **restricts existing circular mobility patterns by preventing onward migration and trying to limit attempted re-migration or re-entry** after instances of coerced migration.

Overall, return governance actors often operate in a securitized manner, where **secretive, extra-legal non-entrée and return practices are legitimized with reference to criminalization, terrorism, and national security threats**, occurring largely with impunity. This is particularly evident in the case of pushbacks, a routine but highly obscured form of coerced return migration. The opaque coercion of return is enabled by political rhetoric that stresses socio-economic pressures, societal and cultural tensions, as well as security threats to justify coerced return. This reflects what the report describes as a dynamic of self-fulfilling xenophobia. Such dynamics were less apparent in countries with a positive historical experience with migrants or those who have managed to instrumentalize a position as EU ‘donor darling’ based on its hosting of migrants. At the same time, **this securitized logic reflects part of the EU’s policy and practice**: the report demonstrates how – in various ways and to different degrees – the legal, policy, and administrative frameworks governing irregularized migration in regional host countries are developed under the auspices of, and based on, the blueprints of EU migration policy.

Where return migration governance is formalized in policy, there tends to be a disconnect between national policy and local interpretation and implementation, with due process considerations routinely disregarded and **return directives sometimes functioning as blanket legitimization** for all kinds of local practices of eviction, expulsion, and exploitation. Here, the report notes **an important distinction between those humanitarian migrants designated as refugees and those who are not**. This is another point where EU influence on regional coerced return migration governance manifests itself. While all humanitarian migrants face similar forms of multifaceted coerced return migration governance, those designated as refugees are more likely to be presented as voluntary. This is probably done to assuage EU donors and diplomatic counterparts concerned with the non-refoulement principle – or, possibly, their own **potential complicity in forms of chain refoulement**.

The securitized, informal forms of coerced return migration governance that leverage marginalization as a key return strategy that the report discusses use **the deliberate erosion of migrant protection to coerce return**. In doing so, coerced forms of return migration are often presented as voluntary – also to placate the normative position of EU donors and partners. This designation means that such returns risk falling off the radar of **under-capacitated and undermined protection and monitoring agencies**, which further normalizes and institutionalizes coerced return.

Taking a de-centering approach to mitigate the Euro-centric bias dominating most studies in return migration (Stel 2021), the report shows the **contextual specificity** of particular countries, as reflected in the attached country dossiers, and of coerced return migration governance in the African and Middle Eastern regions. But it also captures the extensive entanglement of the EU in coerced return migration governance in these regions. The forms of coerced return migration governance that we have discussed in this report obviously differ in various ways from inter-regional return migration, for instance between the EU and the host countries central to this report. The **scale**, also relatively speaking, of the migrant populations present – and, according to state authorities, to be returned – is often much larger. At the same time **state capacity** for migration management may be less institutionalized, allowing for more hybrid and opaque forms of return governance. The **geographical proximity** of host and origin countries – which in many cases neighbour each other – importantly shapes return governance as well, especially as many of the borders studied are relatively porous. This also means that return migration is easier to conduct in informal and ad hoc ways, making it harder to monitor and scrutinize. Proximity and **porosity**, furthermore, can result in more circular migration, with routine re-entry after return, but also more pushbacks. Geographical and socio-cultural closeness, moreover, may also be reflected in the more direct ‘spillover’ of the conflict dynamics or socio-economic hardships that have produced displacement in the first place, generating specific interests for and modalities of return.

While the *intra-regional* return migration governance – within Africa and the Middle East – studied in this Work Package has distinctive features that may set it apart from the types of *inter-regional* return migration – from the EU to Africa and the Middle East – our findings also highlight the **far-reaching interconnectedness of such intra- and interregional return governance dynamics** (Stel 2021). This multi-scalar, transnationally connected nature of coerced return regimes is a universal phenomenon. In the case of the EU, which is central to this project and report, such interconnectedness is evident in the drivers of return

migration governance, where the EU's focus on both non-entrée and return has increased interest in return within regional host countries. It also manifests in the EU and its partners building operational capacity for border management (often resulting in pushback capacity), operational return governance (through assisted return programs), and return laws and policies (legitimizing deportations), all significantly shaping return governance.

The norms, policies, and practices developed to coerce return in the EU often seem to be both imposed on and emulated by their regional containment partners. The entanglement between return migration governance by the EU and African and Middle Eastern host states also manifests itself in the characteristics of return migration governance, where we see that the actors involved in return migration governance, and the type of policies and practices to govern return, are influenced by EU aid and issue linkage. Specifically, the official focus on the types of return – self-return and assisted return – that are less overtly coerced and may be presented as ‘voluntary’ in combination with the downplaying or obscuring of physically forced returns – pushbacks and deportations – partly appear to resonate with EU preference and practice. The interrelatedness of *intra-regional* and *inter-regional* coerced return migration governance, finally, also shows in terms of its consequences, where minimalization of protection and instrumentalization of legal and socio-economic exclusion to coerce return, a normalization of coerced return, an obstruction of (circular) mobility, and a ‘migration fixation’ of diplomatic relations feature in both the host country contexts analyzed here and the EU context researched in other GAPs Work Packages.

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Endnotes

ⁱ SRII WP4 Meso-Level Interview, Van-02, cited in Turkey country dossier.

ⁱⁱ SRII Meso Level Interviews, Iğdir-03, cited in Turkey country dossier.

ⁱⁱⁱ SRII Meso-Level Interviews, Iğdir-06, cited in Turkey country dossier.

^{iv} AI, Ibid, cited in Turkey country dossier.

^v SRII WP3 Meso Level Interviews, Istanbul- 03, cited in Turkey country dossier.

^{vi} SRII WP4 Meso-level Interviews, Ankara-04, cited in Turkey country dossier.